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SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

1.0 Metrics of subsampled viruses

Supplementary Figure 1: Temporal and spatial distribution of global A(H3N2) virus WGs (n=1,172) sampled between 1968 and 2021. These were subsampled using strategy1 (SS1) for TreeTime migration and BEAST1 BSSVS analysis. Uganda includes the newly-generated WGs and previously sequenced public WGs. Region names: C.Africa for Central Africa, E.Africa for Eastern Africa, N.Africa for Northern Africa, S.Africa for Southern Africa, W. Africa for Western Africa, N. America for North America, and S.America for South America.

Temporal and spatial distribution of A(H1N1)pdm09 whole genomes subsampled using strategy2 (SS2) for MASCOT analysis.

Among Africa A(H1N1)pdm09 WGs subsampled using strategy 2, 36% (113/317) were from Eastern Africa (excluding Uganda) and 25% (80/317) from Western Africa. Followed by Uganda with 22% (69/317). Southern, Central and Northern Africa contributed 10% (33/317), 5% (17/317) and 2% (5/317) of the subsampled WGs, respectively (Supplementary Figure 2A).

The majority of the global A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses subsampled for MASCOT analysis (strategy2) were from Asia (22%, 123/592) and Africa (20%, 119/592), and North America (19%, 114/592). Europe, South America, and Oceania had 99 (17%), 71 (12%), and 66 (11%) WGs subsampled (Supplementary Figure 2B).

Supplementary Figure 2: Temporal and spatial distribution of A(H1N1)pdm09 WGs subsampled using strategy2 for MASCOT analysis. (A) Africa A(H1N1)pdm09 virus WGs subsampled in 2009–2021 (n=317) and **(B)** Global A(H1N1)pdm09 WGs sampled in 2009–2021 (n=592) for TreeTime Migration and BEAST BSSVS model analysis. Uganda WGs in panel B include our newly-generated WGs and previously sequenced public WGs. Region names: N. America for North America, and S.America for South America.

The subsampling strategy² returned the majority of Africa A(H3N2) WGs from Eastern (32%, 95/295, excluding Uganda) and Western region (31%, 90/295). Uganda contributed 25% (75/295) of the dataset. The least number of H3N2 WGs were subsampled in Central, Southern, and Northern with 6% (28/295), 5% (16/295), and 0.3% (1/295), respectively (Supplementary Figure 3). The majority of global H3N2 subsampled were from Asia (25%, 255/1,039) and North America (23%, 234/1,039). While, Oceania, Europe, South America, and Africa contributed 17% (172/1,039), 16% (166/1,039), 10% (109/1,039), and 9.9% (103/1,039), respectively (Supplementary Figure 4)

Supplementary Figure 3: Temporal and spatial distribution of Africa A(H3N2) viral WGs (n=295) subsampled using strategy2 for MASCOT analysis. Uganda includes the newly-generated WGs and previously sequenced public WGs. Region names: C.Africa for Central Africa, E.Africa for Eastern Africa, N.Africa for Northern Africa, S.Africa for Southern Africa, and W. Africa for Western Africa.

Supplementary Figure 4: Temporal and spatial distribution of global A(H3N2) WGs (n=1,039) subsampled using strategy2 for MASCOT analysis. Uganda includes the newly-generated WGs and previously sequenced public WGs. Region names: N. America for North America, and S.America for South America.

	A. Number of subsampled viral WGs for TreeTime & BSSVS (sampling period)			B. Number of subsampled viral WGs for MASCOT (sampling period)		
Level	Location or Region	A(H1N1)pdm09	A(H3N2)	Location or Region	A(H1N1)pdm09	A(H3N2)
Uganda	Arua	7 (2010–2011, 2013, 2015)	1 (2014)	Eastern	3 (2015–16)	6 (13 Jan 2013, 9 Nov 2015–17 Nov 2016)
	Entebbe	31 (2010–11, 2013–15, 2017–18)	24 (29 Sep 2010–19 Aug 2018, 24 Mar–15 June 2017))	Central–Entebbe	31 (2010–11, 2013–15, 2017–18)	24 (29 Sep 2010–19 Aug 2018, 24 Mar–15 June 2017))
	Fort Portal	8 (2013–2014, 2017)	7 (16 Apr 2014– 18 Dec 2015)	Central–Kampala	45 (2010–11, 2013–15, 2017–18)	51 (28 Sept 2010–10 Jul 2017)
	Kampala	45 (2010–11, 2013–15, 2017–18)	51 (28 Sept 2010–10 Jul 2017)	Northwest	11 (2010–2011, 2013, 2015)	3 (2012, 2014)
	Koboko	4 (2010–11, 2013)	2 (31 Oct–01 Nov 2012)	Western	2 (2014–15)	9 (19 Nov 2012, 16 Apr 2014–18 Dec 2015, 14 Apr 2017)
	Mbarara	2 (2014–15)	2 (19 Nov 2012, 14 Apr 2017)			
	Tororo	3 (2015–16)	6 (13 Jan 2013, 9 Nov 2015–17 Nov 2016)			
	Total	100	93		100	93
Africa	Central	17 (05 Nov 2014–03 Jan 2020)	18 (18 Dec 2014, 30 Mar 2016– 12 Jan 2021)	Central	17 (05 Nov 2014–03 Jan 2020)	18 (18 Dec 2014, 30 Mar 2016–12 Jan 2021)
	Eastern	113 (25 Jun 2009– 30 Mar 2020)	84 (17 Aug 2009– 16 Mar 2021)	Eastern	113 (25 June 2009–9 March 2020)	87 (17 Aug 2009– 16 Mar 2021)
	Northern	5 (24 Jun 2009, 20 Oct 2014, 06 Jan–11 Mar 2020)	1 (21 Dec 2019)	Northern	5 (24 Jun 2009, 20 Oct 2014, 06 Jan–11 Mar 2020)	1 (21 Dec 2019)
	Southern	33 (06 Jun 2013 – 05 Jul 2018, 10 Feb–09 Mar 2020)	24 (1 Aug 1994, 1 Aug 1996, 1 Jan 2015– 22 Jan 2020)	Southern	33 (06 Jun 2013 – 05 Jul 2018, 10 Feb–09 Mar 2020)	24 (1 Aug 1994, 1 Aug 1996, 1 Jan 2015– 22 Jan 2020)
	Uganda	109 (18 Aug 2009 – 02 Dec 2011, 04 Apr 2013 – 07 May 2018)	107 (28 Sep 2010– 10 Jul 2017)	Uganda	69 (18–Aug 2009–2 Dec 2011, 4 Apr 2013–7 May 2018)	75 (28 Sep 2010– 10 Jul 2017)
	Western	84 (16 Jun 2009, 23 Feb 2015– 21 Jul 2021)	96 (29 June–29 July 2009, 22 April 2014– 07 Dec 2015, 02 Oct 2017– 05 Jul 2021)	Western	80 (16 Jun 2009, 23 Feb 2015– 21 Jul 2021)	90 (29 June–29 July 2009, 22 April 2014– 08 Dec 2015, 02 Oct 2017– 26 Jul 2021)
	Total	361 (16 Jun 2009 – 21 Jul 2021)	330		317	295
Global	Asia	123 (01 Jan 2009– 09 Sep 2021)	254 (01 Jan 1968– 01 Jan 1969, 01 Jan 1971– 01 Jan 1975, 01 Jan 1980, 01 Jan 1982–01 Jan 1985, 01 Aug 1987–01 Jan 1990, 01 Jan 1992– 22 Jan 1999, 01 Jan 2001– 21 Dec 2007, 01 Jan 2008– 07 Sep 2021)	Asia	123 (01 Jan 2009– 10 Sep 2021)	255 (01 Jan 1968– 01 Jan 1969, 01 Jan 1971–01 Jan 1975, 01 Jan 1980, 01 Jan 1982–01 Jan 1985, 01 Aug 1987–01 Jan 1990, 01 Jan 1992–22 Jan 1999, 01 Jan 2001– 21 Dec 2007, 01 Jan 2008– 01 Sep 2021)
	Central Africa	17 (05 Nov 2014–03 Jan 2020)	17 (18 Dec 2014, 30 Mar 2016– 12 Jan 2021)	Africa	119 (25 June 2009–21 Jul 2021)	103 (01 Aug 1994, 01 Aug 1996, 29 Jun 2009–05 Jul 2021)
	Eastern Africa	82 (25 Jun 2009– 09 Mar 2020)	54 (17 Aug 2009– 16 Mar 2021)	Europe	99 (01 Jan 2009 – 06 Oct 2021)	166 (01 Jan 1968–01 Jan 1969, 01 Jan 1971–01 Jan 1977, 01 Dec 1980–01 Jan 1983, 01 Jan 1985–01 Aug 1986, 01 Jan 1988–09 Dec 2003, 25 Feb

						2006–06 Nov 2007, 01 Aug 2009–16 Nov 2021)
	Europe	99 (01 Jan 2009 – 06 Oct 2021)	166 (01 Jan 1968–01 Jan 1969, 01 Jan 1971–01 Jan 1977, 01 Dec 1980–01 Jan 1983, 01 Jan 1985–01 Aug 1986, 01 Jan 1988–09 Dec 2003, 25 Feb 2006–06 Nov 2007, 01 Aug 2009–08 Nov 2021)	North America	114 (01 Jan 2009 –07 Oct 2021)	234 (01 Jan 1968–01 Jan 1969, 01 Jan 1971–01 Jan 1978, 01 Jan 1980, 01 Jan 1985–01 Jan 1986, 01 Jan 1988–01 Jan 1990, 03 Apr 1993–10 Nov 2021)
	Northern	5 (24 Jun 2009, 20 Oct 2014, 06 Jan–11 Mar 2020)	1 (21 Dec 2019)	Oceania	66 (13 Jan–01 Oct 2009, 18 Feb 2011–07 Mar 2020)	172 (01 Jan 1968, 01 Jan 1973, 01 Jan 1982, 01 Jan 1985, 01 Jan 1988–01 Jan 1993, 01 Jan 1996–01 Aug 1997, 01 Jan 1999–06 Feb 2007, 01 Feb 2009–11 Oct 2021)
	North America	114 (01 Jan 2009 –07 Oct 2021)	228 (01 Jan 1968–01 Jan 1969, 01 Jan 1971–01 Jan 1978, 01 Jan 1980, 01 Jan 1985–01 Jan 1986, 01 Jan 1988–01 Jan 1990, 03 Apr 1993–10 Nov 2021)	South America	71 (17 May 2009–1 Feb 2010, 19 Apr 2013–16 Feb 2021)	109 (01 Aug 1996, 01 Aug 2001, 01 Aug 2003–01 Aug 2005, 01 Jan –01 Aug 2007, 01 Jan 2009–23 Nov 2021)
	Oceania	66 (13 Jan–01 Oct 2009, 18 Feb 2011–07 Mar 2020)	172 (01 Jan 1968, 01 Jan 1973, 01 Jan 1982, 01 Jan 1985, 01 Jan 1988–01 Jan 1993, 01 Jan 1996–01 Aug 1997, 01 Jan 1999–06 Feb 2007, 01 Feb 2009–11 Oct 2021)			
	Southern Africa	22 (06 Jun 2013 –05 Jul 2018, 10 Feb–09 Mar 2020)	20 (1 Aug 1994, 1 Aug 1996, 1 Jan 2015–22 Jan 2020)			
	South America	68 (30 May 2009–01 Feb 2010, 19 April–08 Jun 2013, 01 Jan 2015–01 Apr 2020)	109 (01 Aug 1996, 01 Aug 2001, 01 Aug 2003–01 Aug 2005, 01 Jan –01 Aug 2007, 01 Jan 2009–22 Nov 2021)			
	Uganda	109 (18 Aug 2009–02 Dec 2011, 04 Apr 2013–07 May 2018)	107 (28 Sep 2010–10 July 2017)			
	Western Africa	47 (16 Jun 2009, 23 Feb 2015–21 Jul 2021)	44 (29 Jun–29 Jul 2009, 22 April 2014–08 Dec 2015, 12 Oct 2017–26 Jul 2021)			
	Total	752 (01 Jan 2009–07 Oct 2021)	1172		592	1039

Supplementary Table 5: Details of the number and sampling periods of A(H1N1)pdm09 and A(H3N2) whole genomes subsampled per geographical regions used for TreeTime Migration and BEAST BSSVS analysis (A) and MASCOT analysis (B).

2.0 Genetic divergence among influenza viruses over time

Supplementary Figure 6: Variation in viral genetic divergence over time estimated by the root-to-tip (RTT) regression and the corresponding bayroot MCMC plot among Uganda (A and B), Africa (C and D), and Global (E) A(H1N1)pdm09 viral WGs subsampled using strategy1, respectively. We had difficulty plotting the global A(H1N1)pdm09 MCMC plot for bayroot in R.

Supplementary Figure 7: Variation in viral genetic divergence over time estimated by the root-to-tip (RTT) regression and the corresponding bayroot MCMC plot among Uganda (A and B), Africa (C and D), and Global (E and F) A(H3N2) viral WGs subsampled using strategy1, respectively.

3.0 Evolution dynamics among a(h1n1)pdm09 viruses

3.1 Phylodynamics of A(H1N1)pdm09 Viruses

Supplementary Figure 8: Dynamics of the relative genetic diversity (N_e) for different genes of A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses sampled in Uganda from 2010 to 2018, estimated by the GMRF Skyride in BEAST1.

Level	Region	Mean/Median relative genetic diversity or $N_e(t)$ (95% HPD CI)	Mean/Median relative genetic diversity or $N_e(t)$ (95% HPD CI)
		A. A(H1N1)pdm09	B. A(H3N2)
Uganda	Eastern	1.0178/0.9933 (0.6087–1.5102)	1.5475/1.4889 (0.7857–2.4067)
	Central–Entebbe	0.5267/0.5008 (0.2869–0.8052)	1.2852/1.2303 (0.7219–1.9794)
	Central–Kampala	0.7817/0.7572 (0.4373–1.191)	1.4707/1.4136 (0.8651–2.2277)
	Northwest	0.8051/0.778 (0.4453–1.2335)	1.4153/1.3457 (0.7558–2.2423)
	Western	0.8289/0.8031 (0.463–1.2305)	1.339/1.288 (0.7062–2.1027)
Africa	Central	1.0664/1.041 (0.626–1.5665)	1.2537/1.2017 (0.6403–1.9553)
	Eastern	2.2428/2.221 (1.673–3.0019)	2.4477/2.3688 (1.2866–3.6444)
	Northern	0.7311/0.7172 (0.4291–1.122)	1.1445/1.1024 (0.5976–1.8626)
	Southern	1.5102/1.4893 (0.982–2.1779)	1.5197/1.4328 (0.7404–2.48)
	Uganda	0.8884/0.8676 (0.5877–1.2513)	2.4533/2.3943 (1.2669–3.7786)
	Western	1.6039/1.5859 (1.0544, 2.092)	2.0326/1.9725 (1.3095–2.9528)
Global	Africa	1.6447/1.6229 (1.1803–2.2058)	3.5833/3.5738 (2.1026–5.1975)
	Asia	9.5875/12.1447 (1.0182–17.79) (ESS=101)	7.5377/8.9271 (1.0284–14.1215)
	Europe	6.2551/1.7473 (0.5624–19.0162) (ESS=120)	1.3491/1.2831 (0.5772–2.3022)
	North America	1.9235/1.8568 (0.9674–2.8318)	1.7577/1.7347 (0.9735–2.461)
	Oceania	1.4088/0.8989 (0.45–2.3985)	6.0083/1.5474 (0.9186–16.6781)
	South America	1.8956/1.6507 (0.4568–4.2733)	2.106/1.9906 (1.0922–3.0994)

Supplementary Table 9: Estimates of relative genetic diversity among influenza type-A viruses sampled from different geographical regions estimated using the MASCOT model. Panel A): A(H1N1)pdm09 WGs sampled in Uganda (2010–2018), Africa (2009–2021), and globally (2009–2021). Panel B): A(H3N2) WGs sampled in Uganda (2010–2018), Africa (1994–2021), and globally (1968–2021).

3.2 Migration events among Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses estimated using TreeTime Migration model

Supplementary Figure 10: Alluvium plot showing the cumulative number of TreeTime inferred migration events among A(H1N1)pdm09 viral whole genomes sampled in 2010-2018 between different Ugandan sites or cities.

	A. Uganda			B. Africa			C. Global		
Count	Event Time	Origin	Destination	EventTime	Origin	Destination	EventTime	Origin	Destination
1.	2009.64879	Unknown	Kisenyi	2009.27529	UNKNOWN	Kenya	2008.80994	Unknown	N.America
2.	2009.73009	Unknown	Kisenyi	2009.34717	UNKNOWN	Kenya	2008.86192	Unknown	N.America
3.	2010.11826	Kisenyi	Entebbe	2009.42107	Kenya	Egypt	2008.88784	N.America	Asia
4.	2010.60983	Kisenyi	Koboko	2009.45479	Kenya	CoteD'ivoire	2008.90432	Asia	Europe
5.	2010.78638	Kisenyi	Entebbe	2009.47944	Kenya	Ethiopia	2009.1506	N.America	Asia
6.	2010.87282	Koboko	Arua	2009.49588	Egypt	Tanzania	2009.30507	N.America	Oceania
7.	2010.93677	Entebbe	Kisenyi	2009.49861	Kenya	Seychelles	2009.32326	Asia	Europe
8.	2011.53404	Entebbe	Kitebi	2009.62738	Kenya	Uganda	2009.32873	N.America	Europe
9.	2011.54169	Kisenyi	Kiswa	2009.90684	Tanzania	Kenya	2009.34679	N.America	S.America
10.	2011.64774	Kisenyi	Koboko	2010.01369	Kenya	Ethiopia	2009.35713	N.America	Oceania
11.	2011.74227	Koboko	Entebbe	2010.57238	Egypt	Koboko	2009.41367	N.America	Europe
12.	2011.81076	Kisenyi	Kiswa	2010.77502	Kenya	Entebbe	2009.41989	N.America	Asia
13.	2011.83268	Kiswa	Entebbe	2010.86339	Kenya	Kisenyi	2009.45476	N.America	W.Africa
14.	2011.89952	Koboko	Arua	2010.86805	Koboko	Arua	2009.47668	N.America	N.Africa
15.	2011.97175	Kisenyi	Entebbe	2010.91506	Kenya	Kisenyi	2009.47942	N.America	E.Africa
16.	2012.55798	Entebbe	Kawaala	2010.93698	Entebbe	Kisenyi	2009.47942	N.America	S.America
17.	2013.30399	Entebbe	Arua	2011.03013	Kenya	Kisenyi	2009.50165	N.America	E.Africa
18.	2013.30664	Kawaala	Entebbe	2011.18524	Kenya	Entebbe	2009.50682	N.America	S.America
19.	2013.55771	Arua	Koboko	2011.38903	Kenya	Entebbe	2009.51231	Oceania	E.Africa
20.	2013.64911	Kawaala	Fort Portal	2011.50666	Kenya	Entebbe	2009.53148	Oceania	Asia
21.	2014.0676	Koboko	Fort Portal	2011.53423	Entebbe	Kitebi	2009.54413	Asia	Europe
22.	2014.36143	Entebbe	Kitebi	2011.54794	Kenya	Kisenyi	2009.56738	N.America	E.Africa
23.	2014.80801	Entebbe	Kitebi	2011.64136	Kenya	Koboko	2009.59449	N.America	Europe
24.	2014.83815	Fort Portal	Mbarara	2011.74246	Koboko	Entebbe	2009.62736	Europe	Uganda
25.	2015.16274	Entebbe	Kawaala	2011.79998	Entebbe	Kiswa	2009.67628	N.America	Asia
26.	2015.30116	Entebbe	Kitebi	2011.81096	Kenya	Kiswa	2009.70408	N.America	Oceania
27.	2015.38592	Entebbe	Tororo	2011.89902	Koboko	Arua	2009.72571	N.America	Europe
28.	2015.51486	Kawaala	Arua	2012.93037	Kenya	Kawaala	2009.82736	Europe	Asia
29.	2015.55047	Kawaala	Nsambya	2013.26705	Kenya	Arua	2009.8772	N.America	Uganda
30.	2015.57239	Kawaala	Entebbe	2013.26793	Kawaala	Kenya	2010.01367	N.America	E.Africa
31.	2015.58609	Kawaala	Entebbe	2013.30685	Kenya	Entebbe	2010.0849	N.America	S.America
32.	2015.62992	Kawaala	Entebbe	2013.42739	Kenya	South Africa	2010.24927	Asia	N.America
33.	2015.73001	Kawaala	Nsambya	2013.52246	Arua	Koboko	2010.33298	N.America	Asia
34.	2015.83266	Kawaala	Tororo	2013.64931	Kawaala	Fort Portal	2010.42244	N.America	Asia
35.	2015.88472	Kawaala	Mbarara	2014.03089	Koboko	Uganda	2010.43129	Asia	E.Africa
36.	2016.11181	Entebbe	Tororo	2014.03939	Kenya	Entebbe	2010.58036	N.America	Uganda
37.	2016.24132	Kawaala	Nsambya	2014.08032	Kenya	Entebbe	2010.58078	N.America	Europe
38.	2017.14116	Tororo	Kiswa	2014.08218	Kenya	Entebbe	2010.5926	N.America	E.Africa
39.	2017.49124	Kiswa	Kawaala	2014.26027	Kenya	South Africa	2010.68764	N.America	Asia
40.	2017.50972	Tororo	Fort Portal	2014.34247	Uganda	Fort Portal	2010.78078	Asia	Europe
41.	2017.83271	Kawaala	Entebbe	2014.36164	Entebbe	Kitebi	2010.78431	Europe	Uganda
42.	2017.86828	Kawaala	Kitebi	2014.53591	Kenya	Mali	2010.86481	Asia	Uganda
43.	2017.88472	Kawaala	Kibuli	2014.69286	Kenya	Ethiopia	2010.90308	N.America	E.Africa
44.	2017.88473	Kawaala	Kibuli	2014.74725	Uganda	Fort Portal	2010.91503	Europe	Uganda
45.	2017.9039	Kawaala	Kiswa	2014.79999	Kenya	Egypt	2010.99996	Asia	Europe
46.	2017.91486	Kawaala	Nsambya	2014.80822	Kenya	Kitebi	2011.01914	Europe	Asia
47.	2017.9313	Kawaala	Kibuli	2014.83835	Uganda	Mbarara	2011.0301	N.America	Uganda
48.	2017.93285	Entebbe	Kitebi	2014.84383	Kenya	Congo	2011.05502	N.America	Europe
49.	2017.93404	Kawaala	Entebbe	2015.1254	Mali	South Africa	2011.13147	Asia	Oceania
50.	2017.94774	Kawaala	Kitebi	2015.16228	Mali	Antsirabe	2011.19722	Asia	Europe
51.	2018.06588	Kawaala	Kiswa	2015.17195	Kenya	Zambia	2011.27942	Uganda	E.Africa
52.	2018.27103	Kibuli	Entebbe	2015.25458	Kenya	Congo	2011.33147	N.America	E.Africa
53.	2018.30938	Kawaala	Entebbe	2015.2772	Kenya	Tanzania	2011.49952	N.America	Uganda
54.	2018.33403	Kiswa	Kawaala	2015.30136	Mali	Kitebi	2011.50138	Asia	Europe
55.	2018.33403	Kiswa	Kawaala	2015.43678	Antsirabe	Toamasina	2011.53226	Uganda	E.Africa
56.				2015.5041	Kenya	South Africa	2011.54792	Asia	Uganda
57.				2015.5229	Antsirabe	Tsiroanomandidy	2011.64783	N.America	Uganda
58.				2015.54792	South Africa	Zambia	2011.72202	N.America	Europe
59.				2015.63561	Kenya	Burkina Faso	2011.72599	N.America	Asia

60.				2015.69587	Tsiroanomandi dy	NosyBe	2011.75541	Europe	Uganda
61.				2015.72054	Kenya	Nigeria	2011.77704	Asia	N.America
62.				2015.72977	Kenya	South Africa	2011.81093	E.Africa	Uganda
63.				2015.74244	Toamasina	Maevatanana	2011.8575	Uganda	E.Africa
64.				2015.74247	Zambia	Congo	2012.21425	Europe	Asia
65.				2015.78082	Kenya	Nigeria	2012.307	Europe	Asia
66.				2015.89863	Kenya	Tororo	2012.40434	N.America	Oceania
67.				2015.92245	Kenya	Ethiopia	2012.44258	Europe	Oceania
68.				2016.07103	South Africa	Ethiopia	2012.49131	Europe	Asia
69.				2016.08327	Entebbe	Kawaala	2012.52728	Europe	Asia
70.				2016.08639	Tanzania	Rwanda	2012.53822	Asia	Oceania
71.				2016.11201	Entebbe	Uganda	2012.58193	Asia	Oceania
72.				2016.11201	Uganda	Tororo	2012.66976	Asia	E.Africa
73.				2016.20491	South Africa	Mali	2012.8441	E.Africa	Europe
74.				2016.21089	Mali	Mozambique	2012.88249	Europe	Asia
75.				2016.25955	South Africa	Antananarivo	2012.89948	Europe	Uganda
76.				2016.26228	South Africa	Mali	2012.9781	Asia	Oceania
77.				2016.27867	Antsirabe	Moramanga	2013.10681	Asia	Oceania
78.				2016.33331	South Africa	Congo	2013.18902	Asia	Oceania
79.				2016.55188	Antsirabe	Antananarivo	2013.21078	Asia	N.America
80.				2016.56996	Kawaala	Arua	2013.26766	Uganda	E.Africa
81.				2016.63232	South Africa	Antsirabe	2013.32874	Asia	N.America
82.				2016.67236	Kawaala	Nsambya	2013.38902	Asia	Oceania
83.				2016.69793	Kawaala	Entebbe	2013.41642	Europe	N.America
84.				2016.69795	Kawaala	Entebbe	2013.42737	Asia	S.Africa
85.				2016.72352	Kawaala	Entebbe	2013.43285	N.America	S.America
86.				2016.75955	Antsirabe	Antananarivo	2013.49038	Asia	Oceania
87.				2016.82595	Kawaala	Tororo	2013.49861	Asia	Oceania
88.				2016.85165	Kawaala	Nsambya	2013.64642	Asia	Europe
89.				2016.90465	Kawaala	Mbarara	2013.726	Asia	Oceania
90.				2017.05931	South Africa	Burkina Faso	2013.74519	Asia	Europe
91.				2017.16661	South Africa	Congo	2013.76437	N.America	Oceania
92.				2017.17966	Burkina Faso	Mali	2013.84656	Asia	Oceania
93.				2017.42399	Kawaala	Nsambya	2013.8575	Asia	Europe
94.				2017.47186	South Africa	Mozambique	2013.87834	Asia	Europe
95.				2017.50135	Burkina Faso	Mali	2013.89716	Asia	N.America
96.				2017.50585	Congo	Fort Portal	2013.93148	Asia	Oceania
97.				2017.53345	South Africa	Niger	2013.94519	N.America	Europe
98.				2017.61122	South Africa	Congo	2013.96732	Asia	Uganda
99.				2017.61917	South Africa	Kiswa	2014.03834	N.America	Asia
100.				2017.6219	Burkina Faso	Mali	2014.07863	N.America	Europe
101.				2017.63374	South Africa	Kenya	2014.0788	N.America	Uganda
102.				2017.64382	South Africa	Mozambique	2014.08217	Europe	Uganda
103.				2017.68313	South Africa	Mozambique	2014.12746	N.America	E.Africa
104.				2017.69737	South Africa	Togo	2014.15888	Asia	Europe
105.				2017.73934	South Africa	Cote D'Ivoire	2014.21598	Asia	Oceania
106.				2017.75855	South Africa	Kawaala	2014.22463	N.America	E.Africa
107.				2017.78485	South Africa	Congo	2014.23285	Asia	N.America
108.				2017.7871	South Africa	Kenya	2014.26024	Europe	S.Africa
109.				2017.80814	Niger	Nigeria	2014.34519	N.America	Asia
110.				2017.80821	Niger	Kiswa	2014.44108	N.America	Asia
111.				2017.81095	Mali	Niger	2014.54376	Oceania	N.America
112.				2017.86848	Kawaala	Kitebi	2014.64732	Oceania	Europe
113.				2017.88491	Kawaala	Kibuli	2014.71394	Asia	N.America
114.				2017.88493	Kawaala	Kibuli	2014.72326	Europe	E.Africa
115.				2017.90409	Kawaala	Kiswa	2014.75613	Asia	N.Africa
116.				2017.91506	Kawaala	Nsambya	2014.77367	Europe	S.Africa
117.				2017.92786	Cote D'Ivoire	Burkina Faso	2014.77805	Oceania	N.America
118.				2017.92875	Kawaala	Entebbe	2014.8082	E.Africa	Uganda
119.				2017.9315	Kawaala	Kibuli	2014.82737	Asia	E.Africa
120.				2017.93192	Kawaala	Kitebi	2014.84381	Asia	C.Africa
121.				2017.93424	Kawaala	Entebbe	2014.87856	Europe	S.America
122.				2017.94794	Kawaala	Kitebi	2014.90563	Europe	W.Africa
123.				2017.96682	South Africa	Kenya	2014.92284	Europe	S.America
124.				2018.01916	South Africa	Tanzania	2014.93696	Oceania	N.America

125				2018.01917	South Africa	Uganda	2014.99997	S.Africa	N.America
126				2018.04107	South Africa	Nigeria	2015.09585	N.America	S.America
127				2018.09588	Burkina Faso	Mali	2015.10682	Europe	N.America
128				2018.09861	South Africa	Madagascar	2015.1671	Europe	N.America
129				2018.14246	Kawaala	Kiswa	2015.19176	Asia	Oceania
130				2018.14246	Kiswa	Uganda	2015.19449	Europe	Asia
131				2018.17259	South Africa	Madagascar	2015.22463	Europe	S.America
132				2018.19177	Niger	Burkina Faso	2015.27127	Asia	Europe
133				2018.19177	Kawaala	Kiswa	2015.27557	Asia	E.Africa
134				2018.19177	Kiswa	Uganda	2015.27943	Asia	N.America
135				2018.27123	Kibuli	Entebbe	2015.30134	Europe	Uganda
136				2018.30958	Kawaala	Entebbe	2015.31678	Asia	C.Africa
137				2018.30958	Entebbe	Uganda	2015.32745	Asia	S.Africa
138				2018.33424	Congo	Uganda	2015.35318	Asia	S.America
139				2018.33424	Uganda	Kawaala	2015.39552	Asia	S.America
140				2018.37259	Kenya	Tanzania	2015.44381	Oceania	Asia
141				2018.39894	Niger	Nigeria	2015.4986	Asia	Oceania
142				2018.44109	Kawaala	Kenya	2015.55614	Europe	N.America
143				2018.53421	Cote D'Ivoire	Sierra Leone	2015.5945	Asia	N.America
144				2018.61369	South Africa	Kenya	2015.59997	Europe	Asia
145				2018.7149	South Africa	Madagascar	2015.63558	Europe	W.Africa
146				2018.74051	Madagascar	South Africa	2015.69587	Asia	N.America
147				2018.76593	South Africa	Congo	2015.6974	Asia	E.Africa
148				2018.863	Nigeria	Burkina Faso	2015.72052	Asia	W.Africa
149				2018.86848	Cote D'Ivoire	Niger	2015.72327	Asia	Europe
150				2018.86849	South Africa	Mali	2015.74244	S.Africa	C.Africa
151				2019.05563	Niger	Togo	2015.75833	Asia	Europe
152				2019.21917	South Africa	Tanzania	2015.77806	Asia	N.America
153				2019.25205	South Africa	Tanzania	2015.8008	Asia	S.America
154				2019.37642	Madagascar	South Africa	2015.84999	Europe	N.America
155				2019.5653	Congo	Kenya	2015.86249	Europe	N.America
156				2019.63287	Madagascar	Nigeria	2015.87669	Asia	Europe
157				2019.71884	Kenya	Burkina Faso	2015.8785	Europe	S.America
158				2019.72598	South Africa	Togo	2015.89861	E.Africa	Uganda
159				2019.76711	Madagascar	Mali	2015.96487	Europe	Asia
160				2019.80821	Madagascar	Cote D'Ivoire	2016.06828	N.America	S.America
161				2019.89893	Kenya	Cote D'Ivoire	2016.07921	Asia	N.America
162				2019.92875	Burkina Faso	Cote D'Ivoire	2016.08194	Asia	Oceania
163				2020.01365	Kenya	Egypt	2016.08468	Asia	Oceania
164				2020.07103	South Africa	Nigeria	2016.09618	Europe	S.America
165				2020.09015	South Africa	Tunisia	2016.16021	N.America	S.Africa
166				2020.14752	Kenya	Nigeria	2016.18303	Europe	S.Africa
167				2020.16665	Burkina Faso	Cote D'Ivoire	2016.20216	Europe	Oceania
168				2020.18578	Kenya	Niger	2016.20216	Europe	W.Africa
169				2020.19124	Kenya	Tunisia	2016.25954	Asia	Oceania
170				2020.19669	Burkina Faso	Togo	2016.27046	Europe	Asia
171				2020.24315	Togo	Mozambique	2016.28139	Europe	W.Africa
172				2020.25078	South Africa	Niger	2016.31417	S.Africa	C.Africa
173				2020.25135	Burkina Faso	Togo	2016.35243	Europe	N.America
174				2020.76236	South Africa	Nigeria	2016.3579	Europe	C.Africa
175				2020.80484	Niger	Togo	2016.39068	Europe	Oceania
176				2020.87977	Niger	Ghana	2016.41801	Asia	S.America
177				2020.92074	Niger	Nigeria	2016.43167	N.America	Asia
178				2020.97181	Niger	Togo	2016.43167	Asia	Oceania
179				2020.97499	Nigeria	Cote D'Ivoire	2016.47716	Europe	Oceania
180				2021.11506	Nigeria	Togo	2016.55189	Asia	S.Africa
181				2021.21784	Cote D'Ivoire	Ghana	2016.58741	Asia	N.America
182				2021.24931	Cote D'Ivoire	Togo	2016.66727	Asia	Europe
183				2021.26027	Niger	Cote D'Ivoire	2016.69671	S.America	Europe
184				2021.49041	Nigeria	Ghana	2016.70762	Asia	N.America
185							2016.74587	S.America	E.Africa
186							2016.75955	S.America	N.America
187							2016.7814	N.America	S.America
188							2016.79504	Europe	Oceania
189							2016.87391	S.America	N.America
190							2016.8825	S.America	Oceania

191						2016.89341	Europe	S.America
192						2016.90093	Europe	Oceania
193						2016.99998	S.America	N.America
194						2017.06025	Asia	Europe
195						2017.09364	Europe	C.Africa
196						2017.1239	Asia	W.Africa
197						2017.22464	Asia	N.America
198						2017.2356	Europe	Asia
199						2017.29588	Oceania	Asia
200						2017.32327	Europe	N.America
201						2017.3452	Oceania	N.America
202						2017.38459	Europe	Oceania
203						2017.45204	Europe	Asia
204						2017.47128	Europe	N.America
205						2017.48219	Europe	S.America
206						2017.48765	Asia	Oceania
207						2017.49315	Europe	N.America
208						2017.50592	C.Africa	Uganda
209						2017.54519	Asia	S.America
210						2017.54792	W.Africa	Europe
211						2017.55888	Asia	S.Africa
212						2017.56437	Europe	Asia
213						2017.5671	E.Africa	N.America
214						2017.59999	Europe	Asia
215						2017.61917	Europe	Uganda
216						2017.64382	Asia	S.Africa
217						2017.66487	Europe	C.Africa
218						2017.6836	Europe	N.America
219						2017.73699	Europe	N.America
220						2017.73972	Oceania	Asia
221						2017.76971	Europe	Uganda
222						2017.77534	Europe	Asia
223						2017.77925	Europe	C.Africa
224						2017.78082	Europe	N.America
225						2017.79003	Europe	E.Africa
226						2017.80822	Europe	Uganda
227						2017.81546	Europe	Asia
228						2017.83282	Europe	S.America
229						2017.83561	Europe	W.Africa
230						2017.84657	Oceania	S.America
231						2017.85617	Europe	W.Africa
232						2017.863	Europe	Asia
233						2017.86575	Oceania	Europe
234						2017.89076	Europe	Oceania
235						2017.92329	Europe	Asia
236						2017.9589	C.Africa	E.Africa
237						2017.97023	Europe	E.Africa
238						2017.98078	Europe	S.America
239						2017.98903	Europe	S.America
240						2018.00822	N.America	Oceania
241						2018.0089	Europe	Asia
242						2018.01917	Europe	W.Africa
243						2018.01918	N.America	Uganda
244						2018.02455	Europe	Oceania
245						2018.0548	N.America	Asia
246						2018.0685	Europe	S.Africa
247						2018.07873	Europe	Oceania
248						2018.1473	N.America	S.Africa
249						2018.15341	Europe	Asia
250						2018.17808	Europe	S.America
251						2018.29589	N.America	Asia
252						2018.33423	C.Africa	Uganda
253						2018.33425	N.America	Europe
254						2018.38904	N.America	S.America
255						2018.39178	Europe	S.Africa
256						2018.42191	Europe	S.America

257						2018.49728	Europe	Asia
258						2018.54246	Asia	Oceania
259						2018.6137	S.America	E.Africa
260						2018.71505	Europe	W.Africa
261						2018.71551	Europe	S.America
262						2018.79177	Oceania	Asia
263						2018.82191	Europe	Oceania
264						2018.84185	Europe	S.America
265						2018.84749	Oceania	N.America
266						2018.86708	Asia	C.Africa
267						2018.88493	N.America	Asia
268						2018.89041	Asia	Oceania
269						2018.89419	Asia	Oceania
270						2018.90684	Oceania	N.America
271						2018.9178	Asia	Oceania
272						2018.99452	Asia	Europe
273						2018.99587	Asia	E.Africa
274						2018.99725	Europe	N.America
275						2019.00273	N.America	S.America
276						2019.01071	Asia	Europe
277						2019.02352	Oceania	Asia
278						2019.04108	S.America	N.America
279						2019.05768	Asia	N.America
280						2019.07185	Asia	S.America
281						2019.11693	Europe	N.America
282						2019.12594	Oceania	Asia
283						2019.12876	Asia	N.America
284						2019.20274	Europe	N.America
285						2019.21918	Asia	E.Africa
286						2019.22192	Asia	Europe
287						2019.2274	Asia	S.America
288						2019.25204	S.America	Oceania
289						2019.25205	Asia	E.Africa
290						2019.27945	Oceania	Asia
291						2019.28232	N.America	S.America
292						2019.29088	Asia	Oceania
293						2019.33063	S.America	N.America
294						2019.40549	Asia	Europe
295						2019.43014	Asia	S.America
296						2019.43856	Asia	Oceania
297						2019.52054	Asia	S.America
298						2019.52743	Asia	E.Africa
299						2019.57534	Asia	Oceania
300						2019.60118	Asia	W.Africa
301						2019.63014	Oceania	Asia
302						2019.63288	Asia	W.Africa
303						2019.63835	N.America	S.America
304						2019.64418	W.Africa	E.Africa
305						2019.67945	Asia	Europe
306						2019.70587	Asia	N.America
307						2019.71506	Asia	N.America
308						2019.76712	Asia	W.Africa
309						2019.77533	Asia	Oceania
310						2019.79119	Asia	N.America
311						2019.79452	Asia	Europe
312						2019.90136	N.America	Europe
313						2019.90684	N.America	S.America
314						2019.9452	W.Africa	Europe
315						2019.94521	Asia	Oceania
316						2019.95616	N.America	S.America
317						2020.002	Oceania	Europe
318						2020.01365	W.Africa	N.Africa
319						2020.01638	N.America	S.America
320						2020.01639	Asia	Oceania
321						2020.06283	Asia	Europe
322						2020.10928	Oceania	S.Africa

323						2020.13934	Asia	Oceania
324						2020.153	N.America	N.Africa
325						2020.17212	Asia	N.America
326						2020.1776	Asia	W.Africa
327						2020.18578	W.Africa	E.Africa
328						2020.18579	Asia	S.Africa
329						2020.18852	Oceania	Europe
330						2020.19124	W.Africa	N.Africa
331						2020.21584	Oceania	S.America
332						2020.24862	Oceania	N.America
333						2020.2642	Asia	W.Africa
334						2020.48194	Oceania	N.America
335						2020.67834	Oceania	W.Africa
336						2020.7295	Europe	N.America
337						2020.89082	Oceania	Asia
338						2020.91529	Europe	Asia
339						2021.05205	N.America	Europe
340						2021.06274	W.Africa	N.America
341						2021.4904	W.Africa	Europe
342						2021.49862	W.Africa	Europe
343						2021.69862	Asia	Europe
344						2021.70958	Asia	N.America
345						2021.76164	N.America	Europe

Supplementary Table 11: Timing of migration events among A(H1N1)pdm09 viral WGs estimated by TreeTime Migration model. A) Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 WGs sampled in 2010-2018, B) Africa A(H1N1)pdm09 WGs sampled in 2009–2021, and C) global A(H1N1)pdm09 WGs sampled in 2009–2021. For Uganda and Africa analysis the results shown are for when location sites (country or cities) were used as attributes, while for the global analysis the geographical regions were provided as attributes in the TreeTime migration model.

3.3 Migration events among Africa A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses estimated using TreeTime Migration model

Supplementary Figure 12: Alluvium plot showing the cumulative number of TreeTime inferred migration events among Africa A(H1N1)pdm09 viral WGs sampled in 2009-2021 across the different geographical regions.

Origin	Event count	percent	Destination	Event count	percent
Kenya	46	0.25	Entebbe	16	0.09
South Africa	38	0.21	Nigeria	10	0.05
Kawaala	25	0.14	Mali	9	0.049
Niger	10	0.05	Togo	9	0.049
Burkina Faso	8	0.04	Congo	8	0.044
Entebbe	7	0.03	Cote DIvoire	8	0.044
Antsirabe	5	0.03	Kenya	8	0.044
Cote DIvoire	5	0.03	Uganda	8	0.044
Madagascar	5	0.03	Kiswa	7	0.04
Mali	5	0.03	Kitebi	7	0.04
Uganda	5	0.03	South Africa	7	0.04
Koboko	4	0.02	Burkina Faso	6	0.03
Nigeria	4	0.02	Tanzania	6	0.03
Congo	3	0.016	Ethiopia	5	0.03
Egypt	2	0.01	Kisenyi	5	0.03
Kiswa	2	0.01	Mozambique	5	0.03
Tanzania	2	0.01	Niger	5	0.03
Arua	1	0.005	Arua	4	0.022
Kibuli	1	0.005	Fort Portal	4	0.022
Toamasina	1	0.005	Kawaala	4	0.022
Togo	1	0.005	Nsambya	4	0.022
Tsiroanomandidy	1	0.005	Antananarivo	3	0.016
Zambia	1	0.005	Egypt	3	0.016
			Ghana	3	0.016
			Kibuli	3	0.016
			Koboko	3	0.016
			Madagascar	3	0.016
			Tororo	3	0.016
			Antsirabe	2	0.01
			Mbarara	2	0.01
			Tunisia	2	0.01
			Zambia	2	0.01
			Maevatanana	1	0.005
			Moramanga	1	0.005
			NosyBe	1	0.005
			Rwanda	1	0.005
			Seychelles	1	0.005
			Sierra Leone	1	0.005
			Toamasina	1	0.005
			Tsiroanoman didy	1	0.005
Total	182	1	Total	182	1

Supplementary Table 13: Origin and destination cities for migrating A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses between sampled African cities and countries in 2009-2021, inferred by TreeTime migration model.

3.4 Migration events among global A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses estimated using TreeTime Migration model

Supplementary Figure 14: Alluvium plot showing the cumulative number of migration events among global A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses between geographical regions sampled in 2009-2021.

SAMPLED REGIONS						SAMPLED LOCATIONS (COUNTRIES OR CITIES)					
A. ORIGIN			B. DESTINATION			C. ORIGIN			D. DESTINATION		
Origin	Event Count	percent	Destination	Event Count	percent	Origin	Event Count	percent	Destination	Event Count	percent
Asia	117	0.34	North America	55	0.16	England	209	0.37	Entebbe	15	0.027
Europe	95	0.28	Oceania	50	0.15	Kenya	67	0.12	Kenya	13	0.023
North America	70	0.2	Europe	49	0.14	Kawaala	27	0.05	South Africa	12	0.021
Oceania	27	0.08	Asia	48	0.139	Singapore	24	0.04	Bangladesh	9	0.016
South America	10	0.029	South America	40	0.12	India	12	0.02	Congo	9	0.016
West Africa	9	0.026	Eastern Africa	31	0.09	Hunan	11	0.019	Stockholm	9	0.016
Eastern Africa	5	0.015	Uganda	25	0.07	Entebbe	10	0.018	Texas	8	0.014
Uganda	4	0.012	Western Africa	17	0.049	Maryland	9	0.016	Uganda	8	0.014
Central Africa	3	0.009	Southern Africa	14	0.04	Bangladesh	8	0.014	Bolivia	7	0.012
Southern Africa	3	0.009	Central Africa	9	0.03	New Caledonia	7	0.012	Brisbane	7	0.012
			Northern Africa	5	0.015	IIV	6	0.01	California	7	0.012
Total	343	1	Total	343	1	Uganda	6	0.01	Colombia	7	0.012
						Vladivostok	6	0.01	India	7	0.012
						Egypt	5	0.009	Kiswa	7	0.012
						Mexico	5	0.009	Kitebi	7	0.012
						New York	5	0.009	Côte D'Ivoire	6	0.011
						Puerto Montt	5	0.009	England	6	0.011
						South Africa	5	0.009	Nigeria	6	0.011
									Paris	6	0.011
									Singapore	6	0.011
									Washington	6	0.011

Supplementary Table 15: Origins and destinations for A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses that migrated globally between 2009 and 2021, inferred by the TreeTime Migration model. A) and B) All sampled origin and destination geographical regions are shown. C) and D) Shows only sampled locations with at least 5 viral migration events.

	A(H1N1)pdm09 migration to Uganda			A(H1N1)pdm09 migration from Uganda		
	EventTime	Origin	Destination	EventTime	Origin	Destination
1.	2009.627364	England	Uganda	2010.832844	Entebbe	England
2.	2009.877204	New York	Entebbe	2010.870724	Koboko	Arua
3.	2010.302674	Kenya	Entebbe	2010.936954	Entebbe	Kisenyi
4.	2010.580364	Egypt	Koboko	2010.947914	Kisenyi	Stockholm
5.	2010.763974	Kenya	Kisenyi	2011.279424	Entebbe	Kenya
6.	2010.864814	Hubei	Kisenyi	2011.532264	Entebbe	Kenya
7.	2010.870724	Koboko	Arua	2011.534204	Entebbe	Kitebi
8.	2010.936954	Entebbe	Kisenyi	2011.742434	Koboko	Entebbe
9.	2011.030104	Kenya	Kisenyi	2011.899404	Koboko	Arua
10.	2011.534204	Entebbe	Kitebi	2013.267664	Kawaala	Kenya
11.	2011.547924	Hunan	Kisenyi	2013.513424	Arua	Koboko
12.	2011.647834	Kenya	Koboko	2013.649304	Kawaala	Fort Portal
13.	2011.742434	Koboko	Entebbe	2014.052274	Koboko	Uganda
14.	2011.799964	Kenya	Kiswa	2014.342464	Uganda	Fort Portal
15.	2011.810934	Kenya	Kiswa	2014.361624	Entebbe	Kitebi
16.	2011.832844	Kenya	Entebbe	2014.758004	Uganda	Fort Portal
17.	2011.899404	Koboko	Arua	2014.838344	Uganda	Mbarara
18.	2012.899484	IIV	Kawaala	2015.254154	Entebbe	Kawaala
19.	2013.203164	IIV	Arua	2015.574364	Kawaala	Arua
20.	2013.306834	IIV	Entebbe	2015.678514	Kawaala	Nsambya
21.	2013.513424	Arua	Koboko	2015.702324	Kawaala	Entebbe
22.	2013.649304	Kawaala	Fort Portal	2015.711824	Kawaala	Entebbe
23.	2013.967324	England	Entebbe	2015.726154	Kawaala	Entebbe
24.	2014.052274	Koboko	Uganda	2015.832854	Kawaala	Tororo
25.	2014.078804	Maryland	Entebbe	2015.846384	Kawaala	Nsambya
26.	2014.082174	England	Entebbe	2015.884904	Kawaala	Mbarara
27.	2014.342464	Uganda	Fort Portal	2016.111994	Entebbe	Uganda
28.	2014.361624	Entebbe	Kitebi	2016.111994	Uganda	Tororo
29.	2014.758004	Uganda	Fort Portal	2016.377554	Kawaala	Nsambya
30.	2014.808204	Kenya	Kitebi	2017.830564	Kawaala	Entebbe
31.	2014.838344	Uganda	Mbarara	2017.868504	Kawaala	Kitebi
32.	2015.254154	Entebbe	Kawaala	2017.884934	Kawaala	Kibuli
33.	2015.301344	England	Kitebi	2017.884934	Kawaala	Kibuli
34.	2015.574364	Kawaala	Arua	2017.904114	Kawaala	Kiswa
35.	2015.678514	Kawaala	Nsambya	2017.915074	Kawaala	Nsambya
36.	2015.702324	Kawaala	Entebbe	2017.931514	Kawaala	Kibuli
37.	2015.711824	Kawaala	Entebbe	2017.932804	Entebbe	Kitebi
38.	2015.726154	Kawaala	Entebbe	2017.934244	Kawaala	Entebbe
39.	2015.832854	Kawaala	Tororo	2017.947954	Kawaala	Kitebi
40.	2015.846384	Kawaala	Nsambya	2018.024554	Kawaala	Timor
41.	2015.884904	Kawaala	Mbarara	2018.142464	Kawaala	Astrakhan
42.	2015.898614	Kenya	Tororo	2018.142474	Kawaala	Kiswa
43.	2016.111994	Entebbe	Uganda	2018.142474	Kiswa	Uganda
44.	2016.111994	Uganda	Tororo	2018.178084	Kawaala	Parana
45.	2016.377554	Kawaala	Nsambya	2018.191784	Kawaala	Kiswa
46.	2017.505924	Congo	Fort Portal	2018.191784	Kiswa	Uganda
47.	2017.619174	England	Kiswa	2018.271244	Kibuli	Entebbe
48.	2017.745944	Kenya	Kawaala	2018.271244	Entebbe	Uganda
49.	2017.808224	Michigan	Kiswa	2018.295894	Uganda	Ulaanbaatar
50.	2017.830564	Kawaala	Entebbe	2018.309594	Kawaala	Entebbe
51.	2017.868504	Kawaala	Kitebi	2018.345214	Kawaala	Uganda
52.	2017.883994	England	Uganda	2018.389044	Uganda	Bolivia
53.	2017.884934	Kawaala	Kibuli			
54.	2017.884934	Kawaala	Kibuli			

55.	2017.904114	Kawaala	Kiswa
56.	2017.915074	Kawaala	Nsambya
57.	2017.931514	Kawaala	Kibuli
58.	2017.932804	Entebbe	Kitebi
59.	2017.934244	Kawaala	Entebbe
60.	2017.947954	Kawaala	Kitebi
61.	2018.142474	Kawaala	Kiswa
62.	2018.142474	Kiswa	Uganda
63.	2018.191784	Kawaala	Kiswa
64.	2018.191784	Kiswa	Uganda
65.	2018.271244	Kibuli	Entebbe
66.	2018.271244	Entebbe	Uganda
67.	2018.309594	Kawaala	Entebbe
68.	2018.334234	Congo	Kawaala
69.	2018.345214	Kawaala	Uganda

Supplementary Table 16: A(H1N1)pdm09 viral migration events in and out of Uganda in the global context, estimated by the TreeTime Migration model. Results based on analysis of 2009–2021 global A(H1N1)pdm09) full-length WGs.

3.5 Migration rates among Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses

Supplementary Figure 17: Migration rates among Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral full-length WGs sampled in 2010-2018 between geographical regions, estimated using TreeTime migration model with sites in Kampala combined (A) and separate (B).

Supplementary Figure 18: Migration rates among Uganda, Africa, and Global A(H1N1)pdm09 viral full-length WGs sampled in 2010-2018 , 2009-2021, and 2009-2021, respectively, between geographical regions, estimated using TreeTime migration model.

A. MASCOT

B. BSSVS

Supplementary Figure 19: MASCOT versus BSSVS inferred migration rates among A(H1N1)pdm09 viral full-length WGs sampled from Uganda (2010-2018), Africa (2009-2021) and globally (2009-2021).

Origin	Destination				
	Eastern	Central-Entebbe	Central-Kampala	Northwest	Western
BSSVS					
Eastern		1.02	1.10***	1.03	1.25*
Central-Entebbe	0.8		1.86	0.85*	0.88
Central-Kampala	0.76***	1.46		0.84	0.85
Northwest	0.97	0.97	0.92	–	1.00
Western	0.82	0.85	0.81	0.87*	–
MASCOT					
Eastern	–	0.5628 (2.57E ⁻⁴ –1.404)	0.6261 (1.79E ⁻⁴ –1.809)	0.599 (5.94E ⁻⁵ –1.858)	0.5133 (1.07E ⁻³ –1.501)
Central-Entebbe	0.7183 (6.84E ⁻⁵ –2.337)	–	3.8275 (2.61E⁻⁴ –7.4515)	0.8127 (6.33E ⁻⁴ –2.268)	0.4307 (7.04E ⁻⁵ –1.289)
Central-Kampala	0.7428 (1.26E ⁻⁴ –2.479)	0.9967 (4.29E ⁻⁴ –3.926)	–	0.6158 (6.65E ⁻⁴ –1.866)	0.4824 (2.02E ⁻⁴ –1.438)
Northwest	0.7318 (2.55E ⁻⁴ –2.625)	0.5168 (3.44E ⁻⁵ –1.469)	0.5927 (4.18E ⁻⁴ –1.853)	–	0.5904 (7.28E ⁻⁴ –1.738)
Western	0.6879 (2.81E ⁻⁴ –2.374)	0.3278 (1.15E ⁻⁵ –0.981)	0.4555 (2.27E ⁻⁴ –1.361)	0.5729 (2.87E ⁻⁴ –1.919)	–
For the BSSVS model inferred migration rates, highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support. *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), **10 ≤BF <100 (strongly supported), ***100 ≤BF <1000 (very strongly supported), **** BF ≥1000 (decisive). MASCOT: Estimates ≥1 are shown in bold					

Supplementary Table 20: Migration rates among Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral full-length WGs sampled in 2010-2018 between geographical regions, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS and MASCOT models.

Supplementary Figure 21: Migration rates among the 2010-2018 Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses between sampled locations inferred using the BSSVS model for the PB2, PB1, PA, and H1 gene sequences.

Supplementary Figure 22: Migration rates among the 2010-2018 Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses between sampled locations inferred using the BSSVS model for the NP, N1, MP, and NS gene sequences.

between sampled locations inferred using the BSSVS model for the NP, N1, MP, and NS gene sequences.

WG	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	-	0.98	0.95	0.97	0.96	0.98*	0.96	0.99	0.94	0.93	0.96	0.98
Entebbe	0.92	-	0.96	0.97	0.93	0.79	0.91	0.8*	0.87	0.999	0.92	0.95
Fort portal	0.99	0.99	-	0.96	0.95	0.97	0.99	0.95	0.98	0.69	0.97	0.91**
Kawaala	0.97	0.94	0.92	-	0.99**	0.98	0.97	0.98	0.92	0.94	0.93	0.9
Kibuli	0.96	1.37	0.97	1.46*	-	0.96	1.13	1.5	1.0	0.99	1.05	0.97
Kisenyi	1.0*	0.84	0.98	0.96	1.0	-	1.0**	1.08	0.93	1.01	0.98	0.93
Kiswa	0.97	0.96	0.98	1.32	1.09	1.03*	-	1.01	1.01*	1.0	0.99**	0.93
Kitebi	1.00	1.27**	0.97	1.05*	1.06	1.02*	1.34	-	0.97	0.99	1.0	0.97
Koboko	1.28	1.06	0.997**	0.99	0.99	1.0*	0.99**	1.01	-	0.99	1.04*	0.97
Mbarara	0.99	0.996	1.04	0.95*	0.97	0.997	0.98	0.95	1.02	-	0.96	1.01
Nsambya	1.04	1.25	1.03**	1.10	1.01	0.99	1.08	1.02	1.06*	1.02	-	1.11
Tororo	0.96	1.02*	0.92*	0.94	0.97	1.03*	0.96	1.01	0.999	0.97*	0.93	-

Supplementary Table 23: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 concatenated full-length whole genomes (WGs) between sampled location sites in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST. Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software.

PB2	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	-	0.98	0.95	1.04	0.94	1.0**	0.98	0.97	0.94	0.94	0.97	1.02
Entebbe	0.91	-	1.01	0.98*	0.97	0.91	0.9	0.75*	0.82	0.99	0.99	0.93
Fort Portal	0.96	0.96	-	0.94	0.99	0.99*	0.95	0.96	0.89	0.67	0.98	0.96**
Kawaala	0.94	0.79	0.95	-	0.96**	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.95	0.97	0.79	0.97
Kibuli	0.99	1.76	0.98	1.14*	-	0.95	1.17	1.17	0.97	0.97	1.11	1.05
Kisenyi	0.91	0.79	0.99	1.02	0.9	-	1.01**	0.97*	0.9	0.96	0.96	0.996
Kiswa	0.97	1.0	0.95	1.63	0.96	1.03	-	0.98	0.995*	0.96	0.96**	0.94
Kitebi	1.0	1.02**	0.95	1.06*	1.0	1.0	1.56	-	0.95	0.92	1.02	0.93
Koboko	1.28	1.03	1.01	0.96	0.96	0.97**	0.97*	0.98	-	0.99	0.95*	0.93*
Mbarara	0.99	0.98	1.07	0.99*	0.97	0.95	1.05	0.99	0.97	-	1.0	1.03
Nsambya	1.02	1.17	1.03**	1.12	1.04	0.95	0.98	0.99	0.97*	0.99	-	1.36
Tororo	0.97	0.996*	1.04*	1.0	0.99	1.01*	0.99	0.96	1.0	0.95**	0.96	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the PB2. Shaded Red are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 8) but not in PB2 gene.

Supplementary Table 24: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral PB2 gene sequences between sampled location sites in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

PB1	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	-	0.97	0.99	0.96	0.99	1.02*	0.99	0.97	0.996	0.99	0.99*	0.97
Entebbe	0.91	-	0.95	1.00	0.98	0.92	0.97	0.72*	0.88	0.95	0.99	0.93
Fort portal	0.95	0.96	-	0.92*	0.99	0.99*	0.96	1.00	0.93	0.82	0.97	0.95**
Kawaala	0.95	0.87	0.92	-	0.91**	0.95	0.99	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.90	0.95
Kibuli	0.99	1.13	1.04	1.24	-	0.97	1.30	1.12	1.04	1.06	1.10	0.99*
Kisenyi	0.95	0.83	0.98	0.95	0.94	-	0.88**	1.02	0.90	0.97	0.97	0.98
Kiswa	0.98	1.09	0.92	1.45	0.93	0.99*	-	1.01	0.93*	0.97*	0.97*	0.97
Kitebi	0.996	1.09**	0.94	0.997*	0.99	1.01	1.22	-	0.96	0.97	1.04	0.996
Koboko	1.52	1.11	1.00*	0.95	0.99	0.97*	1.01*	0.99	-	1.03	0.95*	1.02*
Mbarara	0.94	1.02	1.06	1.03*	1.02	1.03	1.04	1.00	0.996	-	1.08	1.01
Nsambya	1.03	1.18	1.00**	1.15	1.01	0.97*	1.04	1.04	1.06*	0.998	-	1.03
Tororo	0.98	1.00	0.98*	1.00	0.98	0.95*	0.997	0.99	1.02	1.01	0.95	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the PB1. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 8) but not in PB1 gene.

Supplementary Table25: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral PB1 gene sequences between sampled location sites in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

PA	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	-	1.00	0.95	0.97	1.00	0.99**	0.94	0.96*	0.94	0.93	0.96	1.03
Entebbe	1.00	-	0.96	0.97	0.98	0.96	0.92	0.72*	0.78	1.00**	0.96	0.95
Fort Portal	0.97	0.99	-	0.96	0.96	0.95*	1.02	0.97	0.96	0.67	0.94	0.93**
Kawaala	0.88	0.90	0.91	-	0.95**	0.998	0.95	0.97	0.99	0.996	0.89	1.02
Kibuli	1.02	1.26	0.99	1.53*	-	1.00	1.11	1.43	1.01	1.01	1.05	0.97
Kisenyi	0.95	0.80	1.02	0.996	0.997	-	0.95**	1.01*	0.93	1.02	0.98	0.98
Kiswa	0.94	0.98	0.95*	1.26	1.02	0.98	-	1.08	0.99*	0.98	0.98**	1.01
Kitebi	1.00	0.99**	1.02	1.07	1.05	0.98	1.40	-	0.98	0.95	0.95	0.97
Koboko	1.45	1.04	0.96**	0.96	0.98	0.99*	0.996**	0.97	-	0.98	1.03*	0.995
Mbarara	0.996	0.996	1.09	0.99*	0.98	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.97	-	0.99	1.02
Nsambya	1.08	1.23	1.03**	1.16	1.01	0.98	1.02*	0.98	1.06*	0.98	-	1.09
Tororo	0.98	1.02*	1.04*	0.995	1.01	1.00*	1.00	0.96	1.05	1.01*	0.995	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the PA gene. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 8) but not in PA gene.

Supplementary Table 26: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral PA gene sequences between sampled location sites in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

H1	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	-	1.01	0.95	0.99	0.99	1.00**	0.96	1.02*	1.02	0.96	0.97*	0.96
Entebbe	0.97	-	0.96	0.96	0.98	0.97	0.92	0.72*	0.92	0.97*	0.98	0.99
Fort portal	0.95	0.99	-	0.96*	0.97	1.03	0.96	0.99	0.94	0.70	1.01	1.00*
Kawaala	0.94	0.97	0.84	-	0.91**	1.00	0.93	0.98	0.94	0.98	0.88	0.91
Kibuli	0.99	1.21	1.00	1.48	-	0.96	1.30	1.15	0.99	1.01	1.15*	1.03*
Kisenyi	0.97	0.87	1.02	0.995	1.02	-	0.87**	1.00	0.92	0.95	0.99	0.998
Kiswa	0.97	1.17	0.97	1.14	0.98	0.995*	-	1.02	0.94*	0.99	0.97*	0.98
Kitebi	1.02	1.09**	0.97	1.03*	1.01	0.997	1.10	-	1.04	0.96	1.00	0.89
Koboko	1.40	1.03	1.08*	0.97	1.02	1.02*	1.00*	1.00	-	0.96	1.00*	1.07*
Mbarara	0.98	0.997	1.05	1.02*	0.94	0.97	1.02	1.04	1.01	-	1.01	0.96
Nsambya	1.10	1.16	1.00*	1.44	1.01	0.97*	1.05	1.03	1.06*	1.05	-	1.06
Tororo	0.95	0.84*	1.04*	1.00	1.01	0.98*	0.97	0.99	1.03	0.98*	0.97	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the H1 gene. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 8) but not in H1 gene.

Supplementary Table 27: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral H1 gene sequences between sampled location sites in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

NP	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	-	0.99	0.96	0.995	0.99	0.99**	0.99	0.96	0.98	1.03	0.96	0.98
Entebbe	0.95	-	0.96	1.02	0.94	0.98	0.89	0.74	0.81	0.92*	0.96	0.94
Fort portal	0.98	0.96	-	0.96*	0.98	1.03	0.94	0.96	0.95	0.65	1.00	0.96*
Kawaala	0.95	0.94	0.81	-	0.95**	1.01	0.95	0.99	0.96	0.99	0.87	0.97
Kibuli	1.00	1.44	0.94	1.1*	-	0.97	1.27	1.14	1.02	1.02*	1.14	0.98
Kisenyi	0.96	0.83	0.99	0.98	0.95	-	0.98**	0.96*	0.93	0.96	0.98*	0.97
Kiswa	1.01	1.09	0.96	1.31	0.94	0.92*	-	1.02	0.999*	0.94	0.99	0.92
Kitebi	0.99	0.99**	0.95	1.07	0.98	0.99	1.28	-	0.999	0.93	0.97	1.03
Koboko	1.61	1.07	0.96	0.96	1.02	0.95*	1.02	1.02	-	0.96	1.00*	1.01*
Mbarara	1.02	1.05	1.05	0.95*	0.99*	0.98	1.08	1.06	1.04	-	1.03	1.03
Nsambya	1.03	1.12	1.04**	1.28	1.03	0.98*	1.06	0.98	0.995*	1.00	-	1.09*
Tororo	0.98	0.97	1.06*	0.95	0.99	0.97*	1.01	0.96	0.96	0.93	1.02	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the NP gene. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 8) but not in NP gene.

Supplementary Table 28: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral NP gene sequences between sampled location sites in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

N1	DESTINATION											
	ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya
Arua	-	0.97	0.96	1.00	0.99	0.96**	0.98*	0.94	0.97	0.98	0.99	1.02
Entebbe	0.92	-	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.81	0.96	0.73*	0.84	0.95*	1.01	0.95
Fort portal	0.98	0.98	-	0.99	0.95	0.98*	1.01	0.998	0.93	0.75	0.97	0.96**
Kawaala	0.94	0.82	0.98	-	0.95**	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.97	1.01	0.78	0.92
Kibuli	1.00	1.49	0.99	1.19*	-	0.99	1.21	1.08	0.98	1.00	1.12	0.999
Kisenyi	0.95*	0.99	0.95	0.97	0.999	-	0.98**	1.09*	0.93	0.98	0.97	0.94
Kiswa	0.98	0.95	1.01	1.14	0.97	1.00	-	0.97	0.96*	0.996	0.98**	0.94
Kitebi	0.97	1.07**	0.97	1.04*	0.99	1.02	1.25	-	1.01	0.96*	0.98	0.96
Koboko	1.39	1.01	1.05*	1.01	1.02	1.04**	0.98*	0.98	-	0.96	1.00*	1.10*
Mbarara	0.96	1.01	1.09	0.96*	0.99	0.99	0.97	1.02	0.98	-	0.99	1.01
Nsambya	1.08	1.45	1.02**	1.37	1.04	0.94	1.05	0.98	1.01*	1.03	-	1.08
Tororo	0.99	1.00*	1.01*	1.01	0.98	0.98*	1.02	0.97	0.97	0.99*	0.98	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the N1 gene. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 8) but not in N1 gene.

Supplementary Table 29: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral N1 gene sequences between sampled location sites in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MP	DESTINATION											
	ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya
Arua	-	0.998	0.99	0.995	0.94	0.98**	0.92	0.97*	1.01	1.01	0.94*	0.97
Entebbe	0.91	-	0.96	0.97	0.96*	0.96	0.90	0.78*	0.85	0.90*	0.95	1.01
Fort portal	0.99	0.96	-	0.95*	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.95	0.72	0.97	0.97*
Kawaala	0.97	0.97	0.72	-	0.94**	1.01	0.99	0.95	0.98	0.94	0.90	0.93
Kibuli	1.01	1.09	0.97	1.23*	-	0.97	1.28	1.14	0.99	0.99*	1.20	0.99
Kisenyi	0.96	0.99	0.96	0.94	0.98	-	0.90**	0.99*	0.95	0.93	0.96	0.98
Kiswa	0.99	1.10	0.95*	1.03	0.92	0.98*	-	0.98	0.98*	0.98	0.94*	0.92*
Kitebi	1.01	1.11**	0.998	1.10	0.99	0.94	1.13	-	0.996	0.99	1.01	0.95
Koboko	1.72	1.03	0.93*	1.03	0.98	0.997	1.04*	1.01	-	1.01	0.96*	0.98*
Mbarara	0.98	1.02	1.16	0.98*	0.99*	1.02	1.05	0.99	0.99	-	0.99	1.13
Nsambya	1.02	1.13	1.02*	1.40	1.03	0.94**	0.99	0.98	0.97*	0.98	-	1.03
Tororo	0.99	0.97	1.04*	1.00	0.98	0.98	0.94	0.94	0.97	1.07*	0.95	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the MP gene. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 8) but not in the MP gene.

Supplementary Table 30: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral MP gene sequences between sampled location sites in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

NS	DESTINATION											
	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
ORIGIN	-	0.99	1.01	0.93	1.05*	0.98**	0.99	0.96*	1.03	0.995	1.00*	1.03
Arua	-	0.99	1.01	0.93	1.05*	0.98**	0.99	0.96*	1.03	0.995	1.00*	1.03
Entebbe	0.97	-	0.99	1.00*	0.90*	1.01	0.89	0.70*	0.92	0.97	0.98	0.92
Fort portal	0.999	0.95	-	0.95	0.95	0.93	0.99	0.95	0.94	0.66	0.98	0.98*
Kawaala	0.93	0.93	1.01	-	0.92**	0.94	1.01	1.01	0.95	0.98	0.92	0.91
Kibuli	0.997	1.08	1.03	1.16*	-	0.99	1.22	1.08*	0.97	1.03	1.20*	1.03
Kisenyi	0.94	0.91	1.04	0.98	0.98	-	0.95**	0.97	0.85	0.92	0.98*	0.99
Kiswa	0.99	1.06	0.97	1.22	0.96	0.995	-	1.05	0.92*	1.02*	1.03*	1.01*
Kitebi	0.96	1.04**	0.999	1.11*	1.03	1.05	1.15	-	0.97	0.98	1.09	0.98
Koboko	1.62	1.04	1.07*	0.97	0.97	1.01*	1.01*	0.95	-	0.99	0.97*	0.99*
Mbarara	1.01	1.12	1.15	0.997*	1.03*	1.01	1.1	1.03	1.03	-	0.96	1.03
Nsambya	1.06	1.10	0.99**	1.31	1.00	0.99*	1.01	0.98	1.03*	1.02	-	1.10
Tororo	0.96	1.10*	1.04*	0.99	0.96	0.98*	0.997	0.96	1.04	1.02*	0.98	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the NS gene. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 8) but not in the NS gene.

Supplementary Table 31: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral NS gene sequences between sampled location sites in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

WG	DESTINATION				
	Eastern	Central-Entebbe	Central-Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	1.02	1.10***	1.03	1.25*
Central-Entebbe	0.8	-	1.86	0.85*	0.88
Central-Kampala	0.76***	1.46	-	0.84	0.85
Northwest	0.97	0.97	0.92	-	1.00
Western	0.82	0.85	0.81	0.87*	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software.

Supplementary Table 32: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pdm09 viral full-length WGs between sampled geographical regions in 2010-2018, estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

PB2	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central-Entebbe	Central-Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	1.08	1.17**	1.09	1.25*
Central-Entebbe	0.89	-	1.97	0.86*	0.92
Central-Kampala	0.61***	1.39*	-	0.78	0.86
Northwest	0.92	0.93	0.92	-	0.95
Western	0.86	0.81	0.80	0.85**	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the PB2. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 17) but not in PB2 gene.

Supplementary Table 33: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pmd09 viral PB2 gene sequences between sampled geographical regions in 2010-2018 , estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

PB1	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central-Entebbe	Central-Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	0.97*	1.18**	1.02	1.25*
Central-Entebbe	0.82	-	1.47	0.91*	0.88
Central-Kampala	0.82***	1.19	-	0.75	0.83
Northwest	0.999	0.97	0.98*	-	1.04
Western	0.97	0.96	1.02	0.95*	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the PB1. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 17) but not in PB1 gene.

Supplementary Table 34: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pmd09 viral PB1 gene sequences between sampled geographical regions in 2010-2018 , estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

PA	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central-Entebbe	Central-Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	1.05	1.14***	1.03	1.44*
Central-Entebbe	0.86	-	1.54*	0.89*	0.90
Central-Kampala	0.82**	1.07	-	0.77	0.86*
Northwest	1.18	0.96	0.90	-	1.02
Western	0.84	0.84*	0.84	0.87*	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the PA. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 17) but not in PA gene.

Supplementary Table 35: Migration rates among Uganda A(H1N1)pmd09 viral PA gene sequences sampled in different geographical regions in 2010-2018 , estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

H1	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central-Entebbe	Central-Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	1.01	1.10**	1.04	1.35*
Central-Entebbe	0.90	-	1.71	0.93*	0.90
Central-Kampala	0.80***	1.21	-	0.74	0.82*
Northwest	0.97	0.93	0.91*	-	0.996
Western	0.91	0.89*	0.86	0.94**	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the H1. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 17) but not in H1 gene.

Supplementary Table 36: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pmd09 viral H1 gene sequences between sampled geographical regions in 2010-2018 , estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

NP	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central-Entebbe	Central-Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	1.04	1.10**	1.01*	1.19*
Central-Entebbe	0.89	-	1.67*	1.01*	0.89
Central-Kampala	0.85***	1.23	-	0.87	0.82
Northwest	1.05	0.96	0.99	-	1.05
Western	0.87	0.87*	0.84	0.84*	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the NP. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 17) but not in the NP gene.

Supplementary Table 37: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pmd09 viral NP gene sequences between sampled geographical regions in 2010-2018 , estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

N1	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central-Entebbe	Central-Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	1.03	1.07***	1.06	1.26*
Central-Entebbe	0.84	-	1.55	0.85*	0.93
Central-Kampala	0.82***	1.29	-	0.85	0.86
Northwest	1.07	0.91	0.97	-	1.05
Western	0.88	0.87*	0.86	0.92*	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the N1. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 17) but not in the N1 gene.

Supplementary Table 38: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pmd09 viral N1 gene sequences between sampled geographical regions in 2010-2018 , estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MP	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	0.99	1.06***	1.04	1.35**
Central–Entebbe	0.93	-	1.70	0.9*	0.83
Central–Kampala	0.84***	1.21	-	0.86	0.81
Northwest	0.98	0.94	0.95	-	1.17
Western	0.82	0.83*	0.80	0.87*	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the MP. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 17) but not in the MP gene.

Supplementary Table 39: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pmd09 viral MP gene sequences between sampled geographical regions in 2010-2018 , estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

NS	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	1.02	1.14**	1.11	1.22
Central–Entebbe	0.85	-	1.58	0.87*	0.84
Central–Kampala	0.78**	1.07	-	0.72	0.92*
Northwest	0.99	0.92	0.91	-	1.39
Western	0.83	0.89	0.81	0.90**	-

Highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software. Both yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, highlighted yellow are the unique supported migration rates in the NS. Shaded Reds are statistically supported migration rates in the WG (Supplementary Table 17) but not in the NS gene.

Supplementary Table 40: Migration rates for Uganda A(H1N1)pmd09 viral NS gene sequences between sampled geographical regions in 2010-2018 , estimated using Bayesian BSSVS model in BEAST1.

3.6 Migration rates among Africa A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses

	Destination					
A. TREETIME						
Origin	Central	Eastern	Northern	Southern	Uganda	Western
Central	0	0.139	0.204	0.2404	0.1265	0.0739
Eastern	0.1944	0	0.1848	0.4423	0.3477	0.2658
Northern	0.1216	0.0788	0	0.1024	0.0669	0.1779
Southern	0.2431	0.3199	0.1736	0	0.0679	0.1916
Uganda	0.2691	0.5293	0.2388	0.1429	0	0.0776
Western	0.1419	0.3651	0.5729	0.364	0.0701	0
B. BSSVS						
	Central	Eastern	Northern	Southern	Uganda	Western
Central	–	0.9702	1.1066	0.9698	0.7571**	0.9424
Eastern	0.9828	–	0.8336	0.8388	0.5559****	1.0109
Northern	0.9709	3.3647***	–	1.2895*	0.9874*	2.2464**
Southern	0.5782***	1.1517*	0.8759*	–	0.7644	0.9544*
Uganda	0.9638	0.4897**	0.843	0.5938*	–	0.9615
Western	0.8698	0.8988	0.7436	0.7998	0.7229	–
C. MASCOT						
Central		0.0708	0.1131	0.2556	0.4468	0.1006
Eastern	0.1823		0.0761	0.0871	0.2087	0.071
Northern	0.9538	0.9772		1.1182	0.3777	1.0672
Southern	0.4102	0.0543	0.2302		0.2828	0.1616
Uganda	0.1895	0.042	0.0566	0.0951		0.0933
Western	0.1904	0.0615	0.0944	0.1289	0.4161	

Supplementary Table 41: Migration rates for Africa A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses between sampled geographical regions in 2009-2021, estimated using TreeTime Migration, BSSVS, and MASCOT models fitted on viral full-length WGs. For BSSVS analysis, highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support (Bayes Factor, BF): * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes), estimated using SPREAD3 software.

3.7 Migration rates among global A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses

WG	DESTINATION										
ORIGIN	Asia	Central Africa	Eastern Africa	Europe	Northern Africa	North America	Oceania	Southern Africa	South America	Uganda	Western Africa
Asia	–	0.0578	0.052	0.4514	0.0491	0.2794	0.4551	0.0926	0.0797	0.037	0.0843
Central Africa	0.0468	–	0.0495	0.0763	0.0769	0.0261	0.0483	0.1153	0.043	0.0698	0.0487
Eastern Africa	0.1071	0.1261	–	0.1073	0.1345	0.1531	0.1107	0.0777	0.0841	0.1666	0.1236
Europe	0.3817	0.0797	0.0441	–	0.0438	0.2575	0.2447	0.0942	0.1605	0.0743	0.1723
Northern Africa	0.0289	0.0558	0.0383	0.0304	–	0.0445	0.044	0.0537	0.0424	0.0434	0.0896
North America	0.3349	0.0387	0.0891	0.365	0.0909	–	0.2416	0.088	0.2492	0.0713	0.0632
Oceania	0.3742	0.049	0.0442	0.2379	0.0616	0.1658	–	0.0538	0.0832	0.0269	0.0533
Southern Africa	0.0797	0.1228	0.0325	0.0959	0.0787	0.0633	0.0563	–	0.046	0.0345	0.0489
South America	0.1088	0.0725	0.0557	0.2592	0.0984	0.2839	0.1382	0.0729	–	0.0361	0.0524
Uganda	0.0706	0.1644	0.1541	0.1676	0.141	0.1133	0.0624	0.0764	0.0503	–	0.061
Western Africa	0.0752	0.0537	0.0535	0.1817	0.136	0.047	0.0578	0.0506	0.0342	0.0286	–

Supplementary Table 42: Migration rates for global A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses between sampled geographical regions in 2009-2021, estimated using TreeTime Migration model fitted on viral full-length WGs.

WG	DESTINATION					
ORIGIN	Africa	Asia	Europe	North America	Oceania	South America
Africa	–	0.0326 (2.17E ⁻⁷ –0.1469)	0.0934 (3.91E ⁻⁵ –0.388)	0.0388 (9.46E ⁻⁵ –0.117)	0.0446 (1.15E ⁻⁴ –0.148)	0.0568 (1.01E ⁻⁵ –0.17)
Asia	0.1507 (3.71E ⁻⁵ –0.414)	–	1.4102 (7.74E ⁻⁴ –4.059)	0.3186 (5.88E ⁻⁴ –0.959)	0.8544 (8.96E ⁻⁴ –2.149)	0.3431 (2.92E ⁻⁵ –1.01)
Europe	0.4087 (2.69E ⁻³ –0.946)	2.2046 (2.48E ⁻⁵ –7.203)	–	0.8575 (8.3E ⁻⁴ –2.212)	1.3364 (5.33E ⁻⁴ –3.154)	0.4776 (6.25E ⁻⁴ –1.239)
North America	0.1079 (3.51E ⁻⁵ –0.277)	0.1572 (3.33E ⁻⁴ –0.688)	0.2298 (2.49E ⁻⁵ –0.925)	–	0.3046 (8.57E ⁻⁴ –1.134)	0.3194 (2.88E ⁻³ –0.814)
Oceania	0.4798 (4.17E ⁻⁴ –0.89)	0.8112 (2.62E ⁻⁴ –1.724)	1.2948 (2.55E ⁻⁵ –2.499)	1.3499 (1.05E ⁻³ –2.394)	–	0.503 (7.62E ⁻⁵ –1.037)
South America	0.0553 (2.04E ⁻⁵ –0.163)	0.0524 (6.3E ⁻⁵ –0.2208)	0.0785 (6.56E ⁻⁵ –0.259)	0.1177 (2.16E ⁻⁵ –0.343)	0.1046 (8.12E ⁻⁵ –0.342)	–

Supplementary Table 43: Migration rates for global A(H1N1)pdm09 viruses between sampled geographical regions in 2009-2021, estimated using BEAST2 MASCOT model fitted on viral full-length WGs.

4.0 Evolution Dynamics Among A(H3N2) Viruses

4.1 Phylodynamics of A(H3N2) Viruses

Supplementary Figure 44: Dynamics of the effective population sizes (relative genetic diversity, $N_e(t)$) for different genes of Uganda A(H3N2) viruses sampled in 2010–2018, as estimated by the GMRF Skyride in BEAST1.

Supplementary Figure 45: Dynamics of the effective population sizes (relative genetic diversity, $N_e(t)$) among Africa A(H3N2) viral whole genomes sampled in 1994–2021.

4.2 Migration events among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses estimated using TreeTime Migration model

Supplementary Figure 46: Alluvium plot showing the cumulative number of migration events among A(H3N2) viruses between Ugandan cities sampled in 2010-2017.

Origin	Event count	percent	Destination	Event count	percent
Kawaala	23	0.38333333	Entebbe	13	0.22
Entebbe	12	0.2	Kitebi	11	0.18
Kisenyi	7	0.11666667	Kawaala	10	0.17
Tororo	7	0.11666667	Kiswa	8	0.13
Kiswa	4	0.06666667	Fort Portal	5	0.08
Kitebi	3	0.05	Tororo	3	0.05
Fort Portal	2	0.03333333	Kibuli	2	0.03
Arua	1	0.01666667	Kisenyi	2	0.03
Mbarara	1	0.01666667	Mbarara	2	0.03
			Nsambya	2	0.03
			Arua	1	0.02
			Koboko	1	0.02
Total	60	1	Total	60	1

Supplementary Table 50: Origins and destinations for A(H3N2) viruses that migrated in Uganda between 2010 and 2017, inferred by the TreeTime Migration model.

A. UGANDA				B. AFRICA			C. GLOBAL		
	Event Time	Origin	Destination	Event Time	Origin	Destination	Event Time	Origin	Destination
1.	2008.91465	UNSAMPLED	Entebbe	1994.58097	UNSAMPLED	Johannesburg	1956.90363	UNSAMPLED	Asia
2.	2009.66517	UNSAMPLED	Kisenyi	1995.44424	UNSAMPLED	South Africa	1958.81946	Asia	Europe
3.	2010.64139	Entebbe	Kawaala	2007.63589	South Africa	Dakar	1959.04476	Asia	North America
4.	2010.74017	Entebbe	Kisenyi	2008.91221	Dakar	Entebbe	1959.04477	Asia	Oceania
5.	2010.79781	Entebbe	Kiswa	2009.14678	Entebbe	Kilifi	1960.04477	Europe	North America
6.	2010.80592	Entebbe	Kiswa	2010.30399	Entebbe	Kisenyi	1960.84632	UNSAMPLED	Europe
7.	2010.8443	Kisenyi	Kiswa	2010.56727	Entebbe	Kenya	1962.04477	Europe	North America
8.	2011.1856	Entebbe	Kiswa	2010.65891	Entebbe	Kawaala	1962.49787	Europe	Asia
9.	2011.4247	Kisenyi	Entebbe	2010.73988	Entebbe	Kisenyi	1962.60347	Asia	Europe
10.	2011.68812	Entebbe	Kitebi	2010.7968	Kilifi	Kiswa	1962.97958	Asia	Europe
11.	2011.73744	Kisenyi	Entebbe	2010.80563	Entebbe	Kiswa	1963.04477	Asia	North America
12.	2011.7513	Kisenyi	Kawaala	2010.84399	Kisenyi	Kiswa	1964.04476	Europe	Oceania
13.	2011.75388	Kisenyi	Kiswa	2011.10469	Entebbe	Kilifi	1964.04478	Europe	Asia
14.	2011.77305	Entebbe	Kisenyi	2011.45711	Kisenyi	Entebbe	1964.04478	Europe	North America
15.	2011.81141	Entebbe	Kiswa	2011.51729	Entebbe	Kilifi	1964.3564	Asia	North America
16.	2011.81689	Entebbe	Kiswa	2011.68782	Entebbe	Kitebi	1964.75649	Asia	North America
17.	2011.83881	Entebbe	Kiswa	2011.73714	Kisenyi	Entebbe	1966.04477	North America	Europe
18.	2012.2649	Kiswa	Entebbe	2011.73893	Kilifi	Kiswa	1966.96213	Asia	North America
19.	2012.32379	Entebbe	Kawaala	2011.75358	Kisenyi	Kiswa	1967.04475	Asia	North America
20.	2012.47868	Kisenyi	Kawaala	2011.77276	Entebbe	Kisenyi	1967.04475	Asia	Europe
21.	2012.48081	Kiswa	Koboko	2011.81111	Entebbe	Kiswa	1968.04476	North America	Europe
22.	2012.58018	Kawaala	Nsambya	2011.81659	Entebbe	Kiswa	1969.32386	North America	Asia
23.	2012.59608	Kiswa	Kawaala	2011.83851	Entebbe	Kiswa	1970.48038	Asia	Europe
24.	2012.60701	Kawaala	Entebbe	2012.024	Entebbe	Kawaala	1971.04476	Europe	North America
25.	2012.72176	Kiswa	Kitebi	2012.1177	Entebbe	MUWRP	1971.48379	Europe	Asia
26.	2012.8335	Kawaala	Mbarara	2012.29221	Kiswa	Entebbe	1972.08108	Asia	Europe
27.	2012.87517	Kisenyi	Tororo	2012.34594	Entebbe	Kawaala	1973.04476	Europe	Oceania
28.	2012.94034	Kawaala	Kitebi	2012.48505	Kisenyi	Kawaala	1973.27699	Europe	Asia
29.	2012.95946	Kawaala	Kitebi	2012.54004	MUWRP	Koboko	1975.52657	Asia	Europe
30.	2013.1895	Kawaala	Entebbe	2012.57148	Kisenyi	Tororo	1975.54007	Asia	Europe
31.	2013.24976	Kawaala	Kitebi	2012.59578	Kiswa	Kawaala	1976.04476	Europe	North America
32.	2013.33961	Kawaala	Fort Portal	2012.6067	Kawaala	Entebbe	1976.04476	Asia	Oceania
33.	2013.89538	Kawaala	Entebbe	2012.72147	Kilifi	Kitebi	1977.01336	Asia	Europe
34.	2013.91824	Fort Portal	Tororo	2012.90015	Kawaala	Nsambya	1977.04475	Europe	North America
35.	2013.921	Kawaala	Entebbe	2012.94005	Kawaala	Kitebi	1978.67043	Asia	Oceania
36.	2013.98711	Kawaala	Entebbe	2012.95918	Kawaala	Kitebi	1979.04475	Asia	Oceania
37.	2014.17012	Kawaala	Fort Portal	2013.06835	Kawaala	Nigeria	1979.04475	Asia	North America
38.	2014.3073	Kawaala	Entebbe	2013.1892	Kawaala	Entebbe	1979.04476	Asia	Europe
39.	2014.40944	Kawaala	Arua	2013.24947	Kawaala	Kitebi	1979.14038	Asia	Europe
40.	2014.79526	Tororo	Fort Portal	2013.73441	Nigeria	AddisAbaba	1979.20869	Asia	Europe
41.	2014.86346	Entebbe	Kitebi	2013.84865	Kawaala	Ethiopia	1980.04474	Oceania	Asia
42.	2015.06487	Tororo	Kawaala	2013.92071	Kawaala	Entebbe	1980.04475	Asia	Europe
43.	2015.43997	Kawaala	Entebbe	2013.94886	Kawaala	Entebbe	1980.04475	Oceania	North America
44.	2015.85524	Kawaala	Tororo	2013.95234	Nigeria	Mali	1980.43866	Oceania	Europe
45.	2015.85524	Arua	Fort Portal	2014.00016	Kawaala	Uganda	1980.99671	Oceania	Europe
46.	2015.91278	Tororo	Fort Portal	2014.03186	Kawaala	Entebbe	1981.04474	Oceania	North America

47.	2015.92576	Mbarara	Kawaala	2014.14364	Kawaala	Fort Portal	1981.04475	Europe	Asia
48.	2015.95114	Kawaala	Kitebi	2014.29058	Fort Portal	Uganda	1982.50855	Europe	Asia
49.	2015.95936	Fort Portal	Kibuli	2014.30701	Kawaala	Entebbe	1982.70019	Oceania	Europe
50.	2015.98964	Kawaala	Kitebi	2014.39743	Kawaala	Uganda	1983.04474	Europe	Asia
51.	2016.07479	Tororo	Kitebi	2014.43851	Tororo	Kilifi	1983.29065	Europe	Oceania
52.	2016.20096	Kitebi	Kawaala	2014.4934	Ethiopia	Tanzania	1983.29885	Europe	North America
53.	2016.4376	Kawaala	Kibuli	2014.52816	Mali	Fort Portal	1983.30704	Europe	Oceania
54.	2016.58515	Tororo	Kawaala	2014.5721	Mali	South Africa	1983.56797	Asia	North America
55.	2016.60154	Kawaala	Kitebi	2014.65222	Kawaala	Kenya	1983.58573	Europe	Oceania
56.	2016.65618	Tororo	Nsambya	2014.74651	Fort Portal	Tanzania	1984.04475	North America	Oceania
57.	2016.80781	Tororo	Entebbe	2014.77248	Mali	South Africa	1984.08584	Asia	North America
58.	2017.22511	Kawaala	Entebbe	2014.82539	Tororo	Nsambya	1984.18995	Asia	Europe
59.	2017.27169	Kitebi	Entebbe	2014.84948	Tanzania	Arua	1984.53246	Asia	North America
60.	2017.28264	Kawaala	Mbarara	2014.86317	Entebbe	Kitebi	1984.57087	Asia	North America
61.	2017.29635	Kitebi	Kawaala	2014.9618	Kawaala	Congo	1984.62132	North America	Europe
62.	2017.521	Kawaala	Kitebi	2015.06656	South Africa	CoteD'ivoire	1985.03928	Europe	North America
63.				2015.10594	Mali	Kilifi	1985.62558	North America	Southern Africa
64.				2015.14525	Mali	Burkina Faso	1986.11599	Asia	Europe
65.				2015.22615	South Africa	Tororo	1986.12969	Asia	Europe
66.				2015.23947	Kawaala	Entebbe	1986.78227	Asia	Oceania
67.				2015.25822	Kilifi	Kawaala	1986.79871	Asia	Europe
68.				2015.58648	Entebbe	MUWRP	1986.9297	Asia	Europe
69.				2015.655	CoteD'ivoire	Tororo	1987.12398	North America	Europe
70.				2015.68508	South Africa	Nigeria	1987.62673	Europe	South America
71.				2015.6851	Ethiopia	Antsirabe	1987.62673	Asia	Southern Africa
72.				2015.70701	Burkina Faso	CoteD'ivoire	1987.94367	Asia	North America
73.				2015.76728	CoteD'ivoire	Burkina Faso	1987.98192	Oceania	North America
74.				2015.85497	Kawaala	Tororo	1988.05845	Asia	North America
75.				2015.85497	Tanzania	Fort Portal	1988.05846	Asia	Europe
76.				2015.8577	Nsambya	Tororo	1988.08423	Asia	Oceania
77.				2015.86042	South Africa	Zambia	1988.89518	Asia	North America
78.				2015.86316	Kilifi	Tanzania	1989.02011	Oceania	Europe
79.				2015.91248	South Africa	Fort Portal	1989.05025	Oceania	North America
80.				2015.93166	South Africa	CoteD'ivoire	1989.08038	Asia	Europe
81.				2015.95084	Kawaala	Kitebi	1989.66202	Asia	Europe
82.				2015.95905	Tanzania	Kibuli	1989.78276	Asia	North America
83.				2015.9618	Tanzania	Fort Portal	1989.93792	Asia	North America
84.				2015.97171	Tororo	Antananarivo	1990.00093	Asia	Europe
85.				2015.98716	Tororo	CoteD'ivoire	1990.04476	Asia	Oceania
86.				2016.00958	South Africa	NosyBe	1990.22559	Asia	North America
87.				2016.03294	South Africa	Ethiopia	1990.36337	Asia	Europe
88.				2016.04316	South Africa	Tanzania	1990.71578	Asia	North America
89.				2016.05753	Mali	Reunion	1990.80092	Europe	North America
90.				2016.06249	Tanzania	Kilifi	1990.86342	Asia	Oceania
91.				2016.09606	Antananarivo	Anjeva	1991.05843	Asia	Europe
92.				2016.11219	Tanzania	Mozambique	1991.38629	North America	Oceania
93.				2016.1149	Kilifi	Uganda	1991.56485	Asia	North America
94.				2016.2026	Tanzania	Rwanda	1991.62673	North America	Europe
95.				2016.24332	Tanzania	Congo	1992.11385	North America	Oceania

96.		2016.24552	South Africa	Kilifi	1992.26119	Oceania	Europe
97.		2016.29522	South Africa	Ethiopia	1992.54003	Oceania	North America
98.		2016.29525	Kawaala	Uganda	1992.56805	Asia	Oceania
99.		2016.31436	Anjeva	Moramanga	1992.62559	Oceania	South America
100.		2016.32254	Tanzania	Rwanda	1992.93243	Oceania	North America
101.		2016.34147	CoteD'ivoire	Kawaala	1993.04477	Oceania	Asia
102.		2016.37992	Tanzania	South Africa	1993.08586	Oceania	North America
103.		2016.39905	Tanzania	Congo	1993.12969	Oceania	North America
104.		2016.4209	Tanzania	Congo	1993.19819	Oceania	Europe
105.		2016.4291	Tanzania	South Africa	1993.42402	North America	Europe
106.		2016.4373	Kawaala	Uganda	1993.72408	Oceania	North America
107.		2016.4373	Uganda	Kibuli	1993.73837	Asia	North America
108.		2016.46867	Kawaala	Mbarara	1993.90139	North America	Oceania
109.		2016.50562	Anjeva	Antsirabe	1993.96258	Oceania	Europe
110.		2016.52474	NosyBe	Reunion	1994.3023	Oceania	North America
111.		2016.52748	Kawaala	Kitebi	1994.34339	North America	Europe
112.		2016.60124	Kawaala	Kitebi	1994.49611	Oceania	North America
113.		2016.66138	Kawaala	Ethiopia	1994.55468	Oceania	Europe
114.		2016.66409	Kawaala	MUWRP	1994.62559	Europe	South America
115.		2016.7925	Kilifi	Kenya	1994.66667	Asia	North America
116.		2016.81657	Tororo	Kilifi	1994.86668	Oceania	Europe
117.		2016.87721	South Africa	Tororo	1994.91873	Oceania	Europe
118.		2016.89066	Kawaala	Uganda	1995.04255	Asia	Oceania
119.		2016.91667	South Africa	Entebbe	1995.11307	Asia	Oceania
120.		2016.92637	Kilifi	Kitebi	1995.124	Oceania	North America
121.		2016.92639	Kitebi	Uganda	1995.1368	Asia	North America
122.		2016.9886	Ethiopia	Antananarivo	1995.14039	Europe	North America
123.		2016.99697	Kawaala	Entebbe	1995.59395	North America	Oceania
124.		2017.0562	Ethiopia	Tanzania	1995.62672	Europe	South America
125.		2017.13774	Kilifi	MUWRP	1995.74632	Asia	Oceania
126.		2017.19681	CoteD'ivoire	Niger	1995.87308	Oceania	North America
127.		2017.21387	Kilifi	Tanzania	1996.04477	Asia	North America
128.		2017.22481	South Africa	Ethiopia	1996.15977	Asia	North America
129.		2017.22686	CoteD'ivoire	Sierra Leone	1996.30504	Oceania	North America
130.		2017.27138	MUWRP	Entebbe	1996.4393	Asia	Oceania
131.		2017.28234	Uganda	Mbarara	1996.62286	Asia	Oceania
132.		2017.28235	Kilifi	Antananarivo	1996.62559	North America	South America
133.		2017.29604	Kilifi	Kawaala	1996.74112	Oceania	North America
134.		2017.3207	MUWRP	Kitebi	1996.84478	Asia	Oceania
135.		2017.34812	Antananarivo	NosyBe	1997.02011	Asia	North America
136.		2017.44949	Antananarivo	Toamasina	1997.19546	Asia	Europe
137.		2017.45873	Entebbe	Congo	1997.37328	Asia	North America
138.		2017.46593	Antananarivo	Analavory	1997.45557	North America	Asia
139.		2017.51873	South Africa	Niger	1997.62559	Asia	Oceania
140.		2017.52071	Kawaala	Kitebi	1998.02285	Asia	Europe
141.		2017.52072	Antananarivo	Madagascar	1998.04477	North America	Oceania
142.		2017.58373	Entebbe	Kenya	1998.04478	Asia	South America
143.		2017.65495	South Africa	Mozambique	1998.17903	Asia	Europe
144.		2017.7536	CoteD'ivoire	Togo	1998.24203	Asia	North America

145.		2017.78117	Sierra Leone	Congo	1998.52423	North America	Asia
146.		2017.84486	South Africa	Mozambique	1998.6256	North America	South America
147.		2017.95221	South Africa	Kenya	1998.70231	North America	Asia
148.		2018.00838	Entebbe	Congo	1998.84281	Asia	North America
149.		2018.09059	Sierra Leone	Burkina Faso	1998.89135	North America	Europe
150.		2018.09878	South Africa	Madagascar	1998.99821	Asia	North America
151.		2018.166	Niger	Nigeria	1999.20871	Asia	North America
152.		2018.22261	Niger	Nigeria	1999.26194	Asia	North America
153.		2018.22734	South Africa	Mali	1999.48676	Asia	North America
154.		2018.23029	South Africa	Madagascar	1999.89394	Asia	North America
155.		2018.29648	Mali	Kenya	1999.98131	Asia	Oceania
156.		2018.40566	Ethiopia	Kenya	2000.00943	Asia	Western Africa
157.		2018.6136	Nigeria	Togo	2000.04479	North America	South America
158.		2018.68812	CoteD'ivoire	Mali	2000.06543	Asia	Oceania
159.		2018.69341	Niger	Burkina Faso	2000.1781	Oceania	Asia
160.		2018.69801	Togo	CoteD'ivoire	2000.26436	Oceania	Eastern Africa
161.		2018.73319	Nigeria	Togo	2000.30779	Asia	Oceania
162.		2018.77245	Nigeria	Kenya	2000.36808	Asia	North America
163.		2018.86864	South Africa	Nigeria	2000.62561	North America	Europe
164.		2018.94261	Nigeria	Burkina Faso	2000.71329	Asia	Europe
165.		2018.98697	Mali	Madagascar	2000.83567	Asia	Uganda
166.		2019.03599	Mali	Kenya	2001.02902	North America	Asia
167.		2019.05769	Mali	Burkina Faso	2001.0403	Asia	Europe
168.		2019.06042	Togo	Mozambique	2001.11328	Oceania	North America
169.		2019.09604	Niger	Mali	2001.23483	Asia	North America
170.		2019.10425	Togo	CoteD'ivoire	2001.25912	Uganda	South America
171.		2019.12346	Mali	Niger	2001.29826	Asia	Oceania
172.		2019.16727	Niger	Tanzania	2001.34616	Asia	Europe
173.		2019.17001	Niger	Mozambique	2001.37434	Oceania	North America
174.		2019.17278	Nigeria	CoteD'ivoire	2001.40219	Oceania	Asia
175.		2019.33784	Nigeria	Togo	2001.42559	Oceania	North America
176.		2019.36143	Nigeria	Burkina Faso	2001.44205	Asia	Oceania
177.		2019.41933	Nigeria	Kenya	2001.51306	Asia	South America
178.		2019.56257	Nigeria	Togo	2001.55462	Asia	Uganda
179.		2019.64125	Burkina Faso	CoteD'ivoire	2001.57356	Asia	North America
180.		2019.68321	Togo	CoteD'ivoire	2001.6119	Uganda	Eastern Africa
181.		2019.73714	Nigeria	Niger	2001.71877	South America	Oceania
182.		2019.78372	Togo	Burkina Faso	2001.72822	Asia	Europe
183.		2019.81111	Togo	Niger	2001.74695	Oceania	Asia
184.		2019.82482	Togo	Mali	2001.84251	Eastern Africa	Uganda
185.		2019.84947	Nigeria	Mali	2001.89949	Oceania	South America
186.		2019.85769	Togo	Burkina Faso	2001.9215	Uganda	North America
187.		2019.93314	Togo	Congo	2001.95985	North America	South America
188.		2019.97001	South Africa	Egypt	2002.02012	Asia	Europe
189.		2019.97276	Togo	Niger	2002.06122	North America	South America
190.		2020.05753	Nigeria	South Africa	2002.14616	North America	Europe
191.		2020.15042	Togo	Mali	2002.23516	Uganda	Eastern Africa
192.		2020.17501	Togo	Mali	2002.24605	South America	Uganda
193.		2020.18594	Togo	Niger	2002.26232	Uganda	Europe

194.		2020.42011	Togo	Nigeria	2002.32698	Europe	Asia
195.		2020.77338	Togo	CoteD'ivoire	2002.46763	Uganda	South America
196.		2020.79524	Togo	Dakar	2002.5304	Europe	Oceania
197.		2020.88266	Togo	CoteD'ivoire	2002.68708	North America	Oceania
198.		2020.92012	Nigeria	Niger	2002.72425	North America	Oceania
199.		2020.9537	Togo	Cameroon	2002.85574	Asia	Oceania
200.		2021.32463	Togo	CoteD'ivoire	2002.86132	Asia	Europe
201.		2021.507	CoteD'ivoire	Ghana	2002.92424	Europe	Oceania
202.					2002.9489	Europe	Eastern Africa
203.					2002.97629	North America	Oceania
204.					2003.03383	Asia	Europe
205.					2003.06664	Asia	Oceania
206.					2003.0721	North America	Europe
207.					2003.17047	South America	North America
208.					2003.23057	North America	South America
209.					2003.26063	Europe	North America
210.					2003.27647	South America	North America
211.					2003.29968	Asia	Oceania
212.					2003.32893	Asia	Europe
213.					2003.33167	Europe	North America
214.					2003.38359	Oceania	North America
215.					2003.39178	Asia	Oceania
216.					2003.47783	Asia	Uganda
217.					2003.50822	Asia	North America
218.					2003.53112	Oceania	North America
219.					2003.62616	Asia	Oceania
220.					2003.63493	Asia	North America
221.					2003.65797	Asia	South America
222.					2003.71965	Europe	Oceania
223.					2003.79681	Oceania	South America
224.					2003.80981	Asia	Oceania
225.					2003.84535	Uganda	Eastern Africa
226.					2003.86345	Asia	South America
227.					2003.87743	Asia	Oceania
228.					2003.90271	Uganda	Eastern Africa
229.					2003.92034	Asia	Europe
230.					2003.97823	Asia	Oceania
231.					2004.0262	South America	Uganda
232.					2004.10232	Asia	North America
233.					2004.14341	Asia	Europe
234.					2004.16807	Asia	North America
235.					2004.18725	Asia	Oceania
236.					2004.21465	South America	Oceania
237.					2004.23382	Asia	North America
238.					2004.30505	Asia	Europe
239.					2004.36534	South America	North America
240.					2004.4068	Asia	South America
241.					2004.4598	Asia	Europe
242.					2004.56259	South America	North America

243.			2004.59273	Asia	Oceania
244.			2004.66396	South America	North America
245.			2004.71054	Oceania	Europe
246.			2004.73701	Europe	Asia
247.			2004.77904	Oceania	Eastern Africa
248.			2004.82778	Oceania	North America
249.			2004.85189	Oceania	Asia
250.			2004.95437	Oceania	North America
251.			2004.95902	Oceania	Asia
252.			2004.96534	Asia	Uganda
253.			2005.0393	Oceania	Asia
254.			2005.08588	Asia	North America
255.			2005.09371	Oceania	South America
256.			2005.14341	Oceania	Europe
257.			2005.3078	Oceania	Europe
258.			2005.32758	Oceania	North America
259.			2005.32972	Europe	North America
260.			2005.34615	Europe	Oceania
261.			2005.34889	Oceania	Western Africa
262.			2005.40917	Oceania	Western Africa
263.			2005.44752	South America	North America
264.			2005.45757	Europe	Eastern Africa
265.			2005.46123	Oceania	North America
266.			2005.4667	Oceania	Asia
267.			2005.47154	Asia	Eastern Africa
268.			2005.48315	Europe	Western Africa
269.			2005.49583	Europe	North America
270.			2005.5215	Asia	Oceania
271.			2005.52578	Oceania	Asia
272.			2005.52971	South America	Eastern Africa
273.			2005.58726	Asia	North America
274.			2005.6174	Europe	Asia
275.			2005.62288	Europe	Oceania
276.			2005.64078	Europe	Oceania
277.			2005.64478	Asia	North America
278.			2005.65546	Eastern Africa	South America
279.			2005.65661	Europe	Oceania
280.			2005.66814	Europe	South America
281.			2005.6804	Asia	Oceania
282.			2005.69684	Uganda	Eastern Africa
283.			2005.71876	Asia	Eastern Africa
284.			2005.78802	Europe	Southern Africa
285.			2005.80403	Europe	Asia
286.			2005.82014	Europe	North America
287.			2005.86976	Europe	Western Africa
288.			2005.87218	Asia	Oceania
289.			2005.8941	Eastern Africa	Uganda
290.			2005.90233	Europe	North America
291.			2005.96533	Asia	Oceania

292.			2006.01791	Europe	South America
293.			2006.03242	South America	Eastern Africa
294.			2006.03658	Western Africa	Central Africa
295.			2006.06664	Europe	Uganda
296.			2006.08399	Oceania	Europe
297.			2006.16807	Oceania	Europe
298.			2006.18693	Europe	Asia
299.			2006.20917	Asia	Europe
300.			2006.20917	Europe	North America
301.			2006.21739	Europe	South America
302.			2006.22229	Eastern Africa	Uganda
303.			2006.24018	Oceania	Western Africa
304.			2006.25576	North America	Asia
305.			2006.26125	South America	Oceania
306.			2006.32425	Europe	Western Africa
307.			2006.35439	Europe	Oceania
308.			2006.35712	Asia	South America
309.			2006.38172	South America	Southern Africa
310.			2006.41205	Oceania	North America
311.			2006.41465	Europe	Oceania
312.			2006.46671	North America	South America
313.			2006.49686	Oceania	Asia
314.			2006.54343	Oceania	Asia
315.			2006.54619	Eastern Africa	Europe
316.			2006.55375	Oceania	South America
317.			2006.63384	Oceania	South America
318.			2006.67495	Southern Africa	North America
319.			2006.71603	Asia	Oceania
320.			2006.73521	Oceania	North America
321.			2006.79549	Western Africa	Southern Africa
322.			2006.82014	Oceania	North America
323.			2006.85992	Oceania	Europe
324.			2006.86398	Oceania	Western Africa
325.			2006.8722	Oceania	Europe
326.			2006.89958	Eastern Africa	Uganda
327.			2006.90233	Oceania	Asia
328.			2006.92151	South America	North America
329.			2006.94617	Oceania	Western Africa
330.			2006.95712	Europe	Uganda
331.			2006.95713	Europe	Uganda
332.			2006.97904	Europe	Uganda
333.			2006.98725	South America	Europe
334.			2006.99822	Asia	North America
335.			2007.01818	Europe	South America
336.			2007.03658	Oceania	Asia
337.			2007.04479	Oceania	Europe
338.			2007.06841	Europe	South America
339.			2007.07758	Oceania	Eastern Africa
340.			2007.11038	Oceania	Uganda

341.			2007.1131	Oceania	Asia
342.			2007.13994	Oceania	Eastern Africa
343.			2007.15956	Eastern Africa	Uganda
344.			2007.17048	Oceania	Asia
345.			2007.1896	Oceania	Europe
346.			2007.20326	Oceania	South America
347.			2007.22785	Oceania	Europe
348.			2007.23332	Oceania	Asia
349.			2007.23747	North America	Uganda
350.			2007.26683	Oceania	Asia
351.			2007.28061	Oceania	Asia
352.			2007.28796	Oceania	Eastern Africa
353.			2007.28798	Uganda	Central Africa
354.			2007.2893	Oceania	South America
355.			2007.359	Oceania	Asia
356.			2007.37955	South America	North America
357.			2007.39573	North America	South America
358.			2007.41212	Oceania	Eastern Africa
359.			2007.42457	Eastern Africa	Southern Africa
360.			2007.43278	Oceania	Asia
361.			2007.44369	Eastern Africa	Central Africa
362.			2007.46282	Eastern Africa	Southern Africa
363.			2007.49014	Oceania	Europe
364.			2007.52566	Eastern Africa	Central Africa
365.			2007.53541	Europe	Asia
366.			2007.54391	Oceania	South America
367.			2007.55025	Europe	Eastern Africa
368.			2007.55846	Oceania	Europe
369.			2007.60856	South America	Uganda
370.			2007.6295	Eastern Africa	Uganda
371.			2007.64245	Oceania	North America
372.			2007.64588	Asia	Oceania
373.			2007.67047	Asia	North America
374.			2007.67594	Oceania	Asia
375.			2007.68414	Oceania	Europe
376.			2007.73879	Oceania	South America
377.			2007.73965	Eastern Africa	Europe
378.			2007.74697	North America	Oceania
379.			2007.76337	Oceania	Asia
380.			2007.81714	Asia	Uganda
381.			2007.82347	Oceania	Europe
382.			2007.86095	Europe	Eastern Africa
383.			2007.87345	Uganda	Eastern Africa
384.			2007.90546	South America	Oceania
385.			2007.92183	Oceania	North America
386.			2007.95189	Asia	Europe
387.			2007.95191	South America	Eastern Africa
388.			2007.96011	South America	Asia
389.			2007.97102	Asia	North America

390.			2008.03386	Asia	Europe
391.			2008.04205	Oceania	South America
392.			2008.05282	South America	North America
393.			2008.06945	Oceania	Asia
394.			2008.07767	Oceania	North America
395.			2008.10327	South America	Uganda
396.			2008.14343	Eastern Africa	Europe
397.			2008.14617	Europe	Asia
398.			2008.1763	South America	North America
399.			2008.18675	South America	Uganda
400.			2008.20644	South America	North America
401.			2008.2146	Asia	Europe
402.			2008.21467	Oceania	Europe
403.			2008.22184	Oceania	South America
404.			2008.24205	Oceania	Asia
405.			2008.26818	Uganda	Eastern Africa
406.			2008.28083	Oceania	North America
407.			2008.29358	Asia	Oceania
408.			2008.29686	South America	Eastern Africa
409.			2008.30615	Asia	Oceania
410.			2008.3133	South America	North America
411.			2008.33934	Oceania	Western Africa
412.			2008.34075	Asia	Southern Africa
413.			2008.37082	Oceania	Europe
414.			2008.42329	South America	North America
415.			2008.48316	Asia	Europe
416.			2008.48863	Oceania	Asia
417.			2008.53085	Europe	North America
418.			2008.53794	South America	Southern Africa
419.			2008.57253	Uganda	Eastern Africa
420.			2008.585	Uganda	Central Africa
421.			2008.60917	South America	Oceania
422.			2008.63131	South America	Europe
423.			2008.63658	South America	North America
424.			2008.66076	Europe	North America
425.			2008.68178	South America	Oceania
426.			2008.69959	Asia	Southern Africa
427.			2008.79678	South America	North America
428.			2008.8311	Asia	Europe
429.			2008.84278	Oceania	Central Africa
430.			2008.84479	Oceania	South America
431.			2008.99001	Europe	Asia
432.			2008.99262	Europe	Oceania
433.			2009.01364	Europe	Oceania
434.			2009.05301	Uganda	Central Africa
435.			2009.13521	Oceania	Western Africa
436.			2009.23384	South America	North America
437.			2009.26249	Asia	North America
438.			2009.27495	Oceania	Eastern Africa

439.			2009.29685	Europe	Oceania
440.			2009.30234	South America	North America
441.			2009.31329	Oceania	Europe
442.			2009.31329	Oceania	Asia
443.			2009.35845	Oceania	South America
444.			2009.37844	North America	Eastern Africa
445.			2009.37905	Oceania	Europe
446.			2009.39549	Oceania	North America
447.			2009.39735	Asia	Europe
448.			2009.39812	Asia	Oceania
449.			2009.40918	Europe	Asia
450.			2009.41465	Asia	Oceania
451.			2009.42289	Oceania	Southern Africa
452.			2009.47492	North America	Oceania
453.			2009.48589	North America	Europe
454.			2009.53248	Oceania	North America
455.			2009.55439	North America	Oceania
456.			2009.61719	Asia	Western Africa
457.			2009.63422	Asia	Western Africa
458.			2009.65785	Asia	Western Africa
459.			2009.70506	Asia	North America
460.			2009.71328	Asia	Europe
461.			2009.72358	North America	South America
462.			2009.72972	Asia	South America
463.			2009.75771	Oceania	North America
464.			2009.78452	Oceania	Asia
465.			2009.78454	Oceania	North America
466.			2009.80097	Asia	Europe
467.			2009.8545	Asia	Western Africa
468.			2009.88588	Asia	Oceania
469.			2009.98728	Asia	Western Africa
470.			2010.01192	Asia	Europe
471.			2010.0448	Asia	Oceania
472.			2010.06125	Oceania	Asia
473.			2010.06203	North America	Europe
474.			2010.07767	Asia	Europe
475.			2010.09684	Western Africa	Southern Africa
476.			2010.14891	South America	Europe
477.			2010.1763	Asia	Eastern Africa
478.			2010.18014	North America	Oceania
479.			2010.19822	North America	South America
480.			2010.19975	Oceania	South America
481.			2010.22563	Oceania	Asia
482.			2010.25576	North America	Europe
483.			2010.25577	Asia	Southern Africa
484.			2010.32152	Oceania	Europe
485.			2010.3544	Oceania	Asia
486.			2010.3763	North America	Asia
487.			2010.43111	Asia	South America

488.			2010.46397	Europe	Eastern Africa
489.			2010.46673	Oceania	Europe
490.			2010.46947	South America	Southern Africa
491.			2010.54344	Oceania	Europe
492.			2010.57327	Asia	North America
493.			2010.59823	Oceania	North America
494.			2010.60097	Oceania	Southern Africa
495.			2010.67495	Oceania	Europe
496.			2010.68042	Oceania	North America
497.			2010.69411	North America	South America
498.			2010.74518	Western Africa	South America
499.			2010.78454	Oceania	Europe
500.			2010.84608	Western Africa	Oceania
501.			2010.85029	Oceania	North America
502.			2010.87655	Europe	Asia
503.			2010.93796	Asia	North America
504.			2010.9489	North America	South America
505.			2010.97084	Oceania	North America
506.			2010.98513	Western Africa	Central Africa
507.			2011.01466	Asia	Northern Africa
508.			2011.01468	Asia	Oceania
509.			2011.0639	Western Africa	Asia
510.			2011.07486	Oceania	South America
511.			2011.07806	Asia	Oceania
512.			2011.08032	Oceania	Europe
513.			2011.09669	Oceania	North America
514.			2011.09672	Asia	Eastern Africa
515.			2011.10215	Western Africa	Southern Africa
516.			2011.17594	Europe	Oceania
517.			2011.24697	Europe	Asia
518.			2011.25245	North America	Europe
519.			2011.60186	Asia	Oceania
520.			2011.70225	Asia	Europe
521.			2011.8235	Asia	North America
522.			2011.84806	Western Africa	Europe
523.			2011.86441	Asia	Eastern Africa
524.			2011.92732	Europe	North America
525.			2012.17906	Asia	Europe
526.			2012.24755	Europe	Eastern Africa
527.			2012.25577	Asia	North America
528.			2012.33248	Oceania	North America
529.			2012.34273	Oceania	Asia
530.			2012.35167	Oceania	Europe
531.			2012.47041	Oceania	Europe
532.			2012.50235	Asia	North America
533.			2012.5571	Western Africa	Europe
534.			2012.57629	Western Africa	North America
535.			2012.57629	Western Africa	Oceania
536.			2012.67768	Oceania	North America

537.			2012.70322	Asia	North America
538.			2012.89687	Oceania	Europe
539.			2012.93519	Western Africa	South America
540.			2013.79571	North America	Asia
541.			2014.31843	Uganda	Eastern Africa
542.			2021.89178	North America	Eastern Africa

Supplementary Table 51: Timing of migration events among A(H3N2) viral WGs estimated by TreeTime Migration model. Panel A) Uganda A(H3N2) WGs sampled in 2010-2017, Panel B) Africa (A(H3N2) WGs sampled in 1994–2021, and Panel C) global A(H3N2) WGs sampled in 1968–2021. For Uganda and Africa analysis the results shown are for when location sites (country or cities) were used as attributes, while for the global analysis the geographical regions were used as attributes in the Migration model.

4.3 Migration events among Africa A(H3N2) viruses estimated using TreeTime Migration model

Supplementary Figure 52: Alluvium plot showing the cumulative number of TreeTime Migration model inferred migration events among Africa A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled in 1994 and 2021.

A. SAMPLED REGIONS						B. SAMPLED LOCATIONS (COUNTRIES OR CITIES)					
Origin	Event count	percent	Destination	Event count	percent	Origin	Event count	percent	Destination	Event count	percent
Western	23	0.35	Eastern	25	0.38	Kawaala	30	0.15	Entebbe	14	0.07
Eastern	19	0.29	Uganda	17	0.26	South Africa	24	0.12	CoteD'ivoire	12	0.06
Uganda	12	0.18	Southern	9	0.14	Entebbe	21	0.11	Kitebi	12	0.06
Southern	9	0.14	Central	8	0.12	Togo	19	0.10	Kenya	10	0.05
Central	2	0.03	Western	5	0.08	Nigeria	15	0.08	Burkina Faso	9	0.045
			Northern	1	0.02	Tanzania	13	0.07	Congo	8	0.04
Total	65	1	Total	65	1	Kilifi	12	0.06	Kawaala	8	0.04
						Mali	11	0.06	Kilifi	8	0.04
						CoteD'ivoire	8	0.04	Kiswa	8	0.04
						Kisenyi	6	0.03	Mali	8	0.04
						Niger	6	0.03	Niger	8	0.04
						Antananarivo	5	0.025	Uganda	8	0.04
						Ethiopia	5	0.025	Tanzania	7	0.035
						Tororo	5	0.025	Nigeria	6	0.03
						MUWRP	3	0.015	Tororo	6	0.03
						Anjeva	2	0.01	Ethiopia	5	0.025
						Burkina Faso	2	0.01	Fort Portal	5	0.025
						Fort Portal	2	0.01	Mozambique	5	0.025
						Kiswa	2	0.01	South Africa	5	0.025
						Sierra Leone	2	0.01	Togo	5	0.025
						Uganda	2	0.01	Madagascar	4	0.02
						Dakar	1	0.005	MUWRP	4	0.02
						Kitebi	1	0.005	Antananarivo	3	0.015
						NosyBe	1	0.005	Kisenyi	3	0.015
						Nsambya	1	0.005	Antsirabe	2	0.01
						Total	199	1	Dakar	2	0.01
									Kibuli	2	0.01
									Mbarara	2	0.01
									NosyBe	2	0.01
									Nsambya	2	0.01
									Reunion	2	0.01
									Rwanda	2	0.01
									Addis Ababa	1	0.005
									Analavory	1	0.005
									Anjeva	1	0.005

		Arua	1	0.005
		Cameroon	1	0.005
		Egypt	1	0.005
		Ghana	1	0.005
		Koboko	1	0.005
		Moramanga	1	0.005
		Sierra Leone	1	0.005
		Toamasina	1	0.005
		Zambia	1	0.005
		Total	199	1

Supplementary Table 53: Origins and destinations for A(H3N2) viruses that migrated in Africa between 1994 and 2021, inferred by the TreeTime Migration model. Panel A) Migration events between sampled geographical regions and Panel B) Migration events between sampled locations (countries or cities).

4.4 Migration events among global A(H3N2) viruses estimated using TreeTime Migration model

Supplementary Figure 54: Alluvium plot showing the number of migration events among global A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions from 1968 to 2021.

A. REGIONS						B. LOCATION (COUNTRY OR CITIES)					
Origin	Event count	percent	Destination	Event count	percent	Origin	Event count	percent	Destination	Event count	percent
Asia	182	0.34	North America	137	0.25	England	88	0.102	Netherlands	23	0.027
Oceania	145	0.27	Europe	113	0.21	New York	69	0.08	Victoria	22	0.026
Europe	78	0.14	Oceania	85	0.16	Thailand	57	0.07	Malaysia	17	0.019
North America	52	0.096	Asia	60	0.11	South Australia	48	0.06	Stockholm	17	0.019
South America	39	0.07	South America	49	0.09	Singapore	40	0.05	New York	16	0.0185
Uganda	16	0.029	Eastern Africa	33	0.06	Hong Kong	37	0.043	Brisbane	15	0.017
Eastern Africa	14	0.026	Uganda	22	0.04	Netherlands	35	0.041	Singapore	15	0.017
Western Africa	13	0.024	Southern Africa	16	0.029	Kawaala	30	0.035	Entebbe	14	0.016
Southern Africa	1	0.002	Western Africa	16	0.029	Togo	27	0.03	Hong Kong	14	0.016
			Central Africa	8	0.015	Brisbane	23	0.027	England	12	0.0139
			Northern Africa	1	0.0018	Peru	23	0.027	California	11	0.0127
Total	540	1	Total	540	1	Entebbe	22	0.026	Kilifi	11	0.0127
						South Africa	22	0.026	Kitebi	11	0.0127
						HaNoi	21	0.024	South Australia	11	0.0127
						Bilthoven	14	0.016	Sydney	11	0.0127
						Kilifi	13	0.015	South Africa	10	0.0116
						Bangladesh	12	0.014			
						Argentina	11	0.013			
						Darwin	11	0.013			
						Kitebi	11	0.013			
						Kenya	10	0.012			

Supplementary Table 55: Origins and destination for A(H3N2) viruses that circulated globally between 1968 and 2021, inferred by TreeTime Migration model. A) All events between sampled regions are shown. B) Only sampled locations with at least 10 events are shown.

	A. H3N2 migration to Uganda			B. H3N2 migration from Uganda		
	EventTime	Origin	Destination	EventTime	Origin	Destination
1.	2000.83567	Singapore	Entebbe	2001.45814	Entebbe	Peru (South America)
2.	2001.55462	Singapore	Kisenyi	2001.6119	Entebbe	Kenya
3.	2001.71897	Entebbe	Kawaala	2001.71897	Entebbe	Kawaala
4.	2001.73898	Kisenyi	Kiswa	2001.73898	Kisenyi	Kiswa
5.	2001.78451	Entebbe	Kisenyi	2001.78451	Entebbe	Kisenyi
6.	2001.78451	Kiswa	Kisenyi	2001.78451	Kiswa	Kisenyi
7.	2001.84251	Kilifi	Kiswa	2001.85026	Entebbe	Kiswa
8.	2001.85026	Entebbe	Kiswa	2001.9215	Entebbe	District of Columbia (North America)
9.	2002.51043	Kisenyi	Entebbe	2002.23516	Entebbe	Kilifi
10.	2002.73245	Entebbe	Kitebi	2002.24605	Entebbe	Kilifi
11.	2002.78178	Kisenyi	Entebbe	2002.26232	Kisenyi	Stockholm
12.	2002.79485	Kilifi	Kawaala	2002.35822	Kisenyi	Peru (South America)
13.	2002.8174	Entebbe	Kisenyi	2002.37904	Entebbe	SantoAntoniodaPatrulha (South America)
14.	2002.85574	Entebbe	Kiswa	2002.51043	Kisenyi	Entebbe
15.	2002.86122	Entebbe	Kiswa	2002.73245	Entebbe	Kitebi
16.	2002.88314	Entebbe	Kiswa	2002.78178	Kisenyi	Entebbe
17.	2002.88315	Kawaala	Kiswa	2002.8174	Entebbe	Kisenyi
18.	2003.13362	Kilifi	Koboko	2002.85574	Entebbe	Kiswa
19.	2003.47783	Thailand	Kawaala	2002.86122	Entebbe	Kiswa
20.	2003.54029	Peru	Kawaala	2002.88314	Entebbe	Kiswa
21.	2003.64042	Kawaala	Entebbe	2002.88315	Kawaala	Kiswa
22.	2003.65135	Kawaala	Entebbe	2003.64042	Kawaala	Entebbe
23.	2003.76611	Kilifi	Kitebi	2003.65135	Kawaala	Entebbe
24.	2003.78147	Singapore	Tororo	2003.82073	Kawaala	MUWRP
25.	2003.82073	Kawaala	MUWRP	2003.90271	Koboko	MUWRP
26.	2003.90271	Koboko	MUWRP	2003.9273	Kawaala	Mbarara
27.	2003.9273	Kawaala	Mbarara	2003.98467	Kawaala	Kitebi
28.	2003.98467	Kawaala	Kitebi	2004.00379	Kawaala	Kitebi
29.	2004.00379	Kawaala	Kitebi	2004.23382	Kawaala	Entebbe
30.	2004.23382	Kawaala	Entebbe	2004.2941	Kawaala	Kitebi
31.	2004.2941	Kawaala	Kitebi	2004.57452	Tororo	Paraguay (South America)
32.	2004.96534	Thailand	Entebbe	2004.77081	Tororo	South Australia (Oceania)
33.	2005.00702	Kawaala	Entebbe	2004.998	Tororo	Paraguay (South America)
34.	2005.04478	Kawaala	Uganda	2005.00702	Kawaala	Entebbe
35.	2005.07118	Kawaala	Entebbe	2005.04478	Kawaala	Uganda
36.	2005.19193	Kawaala	Fort Portal	2005.07118	Kawaala	Entebbe
37.	2005.33519	Fort Portal	Uganda	2005.19193	Kawaala	Fort Portal

38.	2005.35164	Kawaala	Entebbe	2005.33519	Fort Portal	Uganda
39.	2005.44204	Kawaala	Uganda	2005.35164	Kawaala	Entebbe
40.	2005.8941	Tanzania	Arua	2005.44204	Kawaala	Uganda
41.	2005.9078	Entebbe	Kitebi	2005.69684	Kawaala	Kenya
42.	2006.22229	Kilifi	Kawaala	2005.9078	Entebbe	Kitebi
43.	2006.27115	Kawaala	Entebbe	2006.27115	Kawaala	Entebbe
44.	2006.6311	Entebbe	MUWRP	2006.6311	Entebbe	MUWRP
45.	2006.89958	Tanzania	Fort Portal	2006.89959	Kawaala	Tororo
46.	2006.89959	Kawaala	Tororo	2006.9955	Kawaala	Kitebi
47.	2006.95712	England	Tororo	2007.30711	Kawaala	Uganda
48.	2006.95713	England	Fort Portal	2007.48197	Kawaala	Kibuli
49.	2006.97904	England	Fort Portal	2007.49288	Kawaala	Uganda
50.	2006.9955	Kawaala	Kitebi	2007.57211	Kawaala	Kitebi
51.	2007.00371	England	Kibuli	2007.60868	Kitebi	Kilifi
52.	2007.00645	England	Fort Portal	2007.64041	Kawaala	Nsambya
53.	2007.11038	South Australia	Tororo	2007.64591	Kawaala	Kitebi
54.	2007.15956	Kilifi	Uganda	2007.70051	Tororo	Nsambya
55.	2007.23747	New Jersey	Kawaala	2007.70872	Kawaala	MUWRP
56.	2007.30711	Kawaala	Uganda	2007.73965	Kawaala	Ethiopia
57.	2007.37238	Kilifi	Kitebi	2007.86871	Kitebi	Puerto Rico (North America)
58.	2007.41212	South Australia	Kawaala	2007.87345	Kitebi	Kilifi
59.	2007.48197	Kawaala	Kibuli	2007.93571	Kawaala	Uganda
60.	2007.49288	Kawaala	Uganda	2007.96011	Kitebi	TOYAMA (Asia)
61.	2007.57211	Kawaala	Kitebi	2007.97102	Kitebi	Uganda
62.	2007.64041	Kawaala	Nsambya	2008.05282	Kitebi	Guatemala (North America)
63.	2007.64591	Kawaala	Kitebi	2008.127	Kitebi	Uruguay (South America)
64.	2007.70051	Tororo	Nsambya	2008.26946	Kawaala	Entebbe
65.	2007.70872	Kawaala	MUWRP	2008.29686	Kitebi	Tanzania
66.	2007.841	Pennsylvania	Entebbe	2008.30506	Entebbe	Santiago (South America)
67.	2007.92185	England	Tororo	2008.31605	Kitebi	Entebbe
68.	2007.93571	Kawaala	Uganda	2008.32701	Uganda	Mbarara
69.	2007.97102	Kitebi	Uganda	2008.3407	Kitebi	Kawaala
70.	2008.26946	Kawaala	Entebbe	2008.42013	Entebbe	Uruguay (South America)
71.	2008.31605	Kitebi	Entebbe	2008.47769	Kitebi	MUWRP (Uganda)
72.	2008.32701	Uganda	Mbarara	2008.54616	Entebbe	MUWRP (Uganda)
73.	2008.3407	Kitebi	Kawaala	2008.56535	Kawaala	Kitebi
74.	2008.47769	Kitebi	MUWRP	2008.585	Entebbe	Congo
75.	2008.54616	Entebbe	MUWRP	2008.60917	Entebbe	Brisbane (Oceania)
76.	2008.56535	Kawaala	Kitebi	2009.05301	Entebbe	Congo

Supplementary Table 56: TreeTime inferred migration events among A(H3N2) viruses in and out of Uganda in the global context (combined with global genome sequences as background data).

4.5 Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses

Supplementary Figure 57: TreeTime estimated migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viral WGs sampled in 2010–2017 between sampled location sites with sites in Kampala combined (A) and separate (B).

Supplementary Figure 58: Migration rates among Uganda, Africa, and Global A(H3N2) WGs sampled in 2010–2017, 1994–2021, and 1968–2021, respectively, between geographical regions, estimated using TreeTime Migration model.

BSSVS inferred Migration rates (WG)												
WG	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Aru a	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kiseny i	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	–	1.03	1.19	1.05	1.08	1.02	0.97	1.02	1.04	1.06	1.07**	1.09
Entebbe	1.00	–	1.00	1.03*	0.97	0.96	0.95	1.05	0.95	0.93	1.01	0.97
Fort Portal	0.86	0.98	–	0.96	0.91*	0.99*	0.95*	0.96	0.95	0.97	0.95	0.97
Kawaala	0.98	0.92*	0.94	–	0.90	0.99	1.00	1.03	0.93*	0.79*	0.96	0.91
Kibuli	0.98	1.01	1.07	1.02	–	1.03	0.97	1.00	0.999*	0.99*	1.02	1.03
Kisenyi	0.99	1.07	1.02*	1.00	1.00	–	1.40**	0.96	0.94	0.96	1.02	1.01
Kiswa	0.93	1.39	0.98**	1.02	0.99*	0.97*	–	1.08	0.88	0.93*	1.00	1.02
Kitebi	0.97*	1.16	0.96	1.32	0.93	0.97	0.96	–	0.95	0.91	0.94	0.92
Koboko	0.95	0.95	0.97	0.99*	0.99	0.98	1.00	0.98	–	0.96*	1.03	0.997
Mbarara	1.02	1.21	1.06	1.15*	1.07	0.99	1.00	1.15	1.03	–	1.00	1.16*
Nsambya	1.00	0.96	1.05	0.95	1.00	0.92**	0.96	1.02	0.95	1.02	–	1.04
Tororo	0.95	0.99	1.00	0.97*	0.90	0.998	0.99	0.97	0.93	0.998	0.83	–

Highlighted green and bold are rates with high statistical support. *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes)

Supplementary Table 59: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between location sites sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the concatenated whole genomes using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

Supplementary Figure 60: Migration rates among Uganda (2010–2017), Africa (1994–2021), and Global A(H3N2) virus concatenated WGs estimated by MASCOT (top panel) and BSSVS model (bottom panel).

MIGRATION RATE (WG)					
ORIGIN	DESTINATION				
	Eastern	Central-Entebbe	Central-Kampala	Northwest	Western
A. BSSVS					
Eastern	-	1.01	1.13**	0.91*	0.99
Central-Entebbe	0.84	-	1.67*	0.80	0.82
Central-Kampala	0.93***	0.96	-	0.89	0.77
Northwest	1.15	0.998*	1.01	-	1.11*
Western	1.06	0.94	1.10	0.84*	-
B. MASCOT					
Eastern	-	0.7229 (6.32E ⁻⁴ -2.181)	0.7852 (7.51E ⁻⁴ -2.286)	0.7966 (3.72E ⁻⁴ -2.267)	0.7193 (1.97E ⁻⁴ -2.153)
Central-Entebbe	0.5143 (2.3E ⁻⁴ -1.668)	-	1.251 (1.24E ⁻³ -3.29)	0.4948 (9.72E ⁻⁵ -1.697)	0.4294 (3.82E ⁻⁴ -1.389)
Central-Kampala	0.5173 (1.02E ⁻³ -1.706)	1.4836 (2.88E ⁻³ -3.603)	-	0.5451 (6.11E ⁻⁴ -1.761)	0.4573 (1.28E ⁻⁵ -1.39)
Northwest	0.7966 (2.78E ⁻⁴ -2.271)	0.7109 (1.84E ⁻⁴ -2.071)	0.8028 (2.05E ⁻⁴ -2.381)	-	0.6931 (2.31E ⁻⁴ -2.067)
Western	0.8271 (3.28E ⁻⁴ -2.351)	0.6791 (3.01E ⁻⁵ -2.026)	0.9326 (8.52E ⁻⁴ -2.71)	0.7222 (5.32E ⁻⁴ -2.249)	-

Supplementary Table 61: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the concatenated whole genomes using the BSSVS model in BEAST1 (A) and MASCOT model in BEAST2 (B). For the BSSVS analysis, highlighted green and bold are rates with high statistical support. * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), * $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes).**

MIGRATION RATE (PB2)												
ORIGIN	DESTINATION											
	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	–	0.96	1.14	1.06	1.10	0.97*	0.96	1.01	0.96	1.02	1.04**	1.05
Entebbe	1.00	–	0.99	0.99*	0.96	0.92	1.04	1.01	0.94*	0.96	0.96	0.92
Fort Portal	0.83	1.01	–	0.96	0.85*	0.99**	0.96**	0.94	0.95	0.98	0.96	0.96
Kawaala	0.99	0.91*	0.93	–	0.99	0.99	1.03	1.03	0.93*	0.84	0.99	0.85
Kibuli	1.07	0.999	1.15	1.07*	–	0.95	1.00	1.04	1.00*	1.00*	0.997	1.08
Kisenyi	1.00	1.17	1.00*	1.02	0.98	–	1.37*	0.99	0.97	1.01	1.01	0.96
Kiswa	1.00	1.21	0.96**	0.98	1.00*	0.95*	–	0.98	0.86	0.96	0.97	0.94
Kitebi	0.90	1.13	0.94	1.28	0.91	0.98	0.97	–	0.94	0.86	0.95	0.95
Koboko	1.02	1.00*	1.04	1.01*	0.99	1.02	1.01	1.00	–	1.00	1.03	1.06
Mbarara	0.97	1.15	1.10	1.18	1.09	0.96	0.96	1.09	0.999	–	0.99	1.20**
Nsambya	0.96*	0.98	1.01	1.02	1.01	0.97**	0.99	0.99	0.99	1.03	–	1.03
Tororo	0.99	0.95	0.93	0.96	0.97	0.97	0.99	0.999	0.93	0.97	0.75	–

Statistical support: *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the PB2 gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 33) but not in the PB2 gene.

Supplementary Table 62: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between location sites sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the PB2 gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (PB1)												
ORIGIN	DESTINATION											
	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	–	1.04	1.06	1.07	1.05	0.97*	0.98	1.00	1.10	1.05	1.05**	1.12
Entebbe	0.9	–	0.97	0.99*	0.93	0.97	0.95	0.98	0.92	0.90	0.98	0.97
Fort Portal	0.91	1.02	–	0.95	0.93*	0.94*	0.95**	0.98	0.98	0.996	0.93	0.93
Kawaala	0.96	0.91*	0.92	–	0.87	1.00	1.01	1.11	0.92	0.82*	0.93	0.93
Kibuli	1.01	1.08	1.04	1.11*	–	0.96*	0.97	1.04	1.02*	1.06*	1.02	1.1
Kisenyi	1.00	1.05	0.97*	1.04	0.96	–	1.22*	1.01	1.00	0.995	0.97	0.95
Kiswa	1.00	1.13	0.97**	0.996	0.96*	0.90*	–	0.99	0.92	0.95*	0.94	0.95
Kitebi	0.95	1.04	0.96	1.36	0.92	0.97	0.99	–	0.92	0.95	1.01	0.95
Koboko	0.98	1.05	1.06	1.03*	0.98	0.98	0.999	0.98	–	1.02	0.99	1.01
Mbarara	1.03	1.16	1.09	1.14	1.08	0.96	1.02	1.10	1.00	–	1.00	1.12*
Nsambya	0.96	1.02	1.04	1.00	1.05	0.96**	0.98	0.999	0.97	1.00	–	1.01
Tororo	0.92	0.98	1.01	0.99	0.94	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.01	0.86	–

Statistical support: *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the PB1 gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 33) but not in the PB1 gene.

Supplementary Table 63: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between location sites sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the PB1 gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (PA)												
	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	–	0.996	1.29	0.99	1.07	0.95	0.99	1.04	1.01	0.99	1.04***	1.11
Entebbe	0.96	–	0.99	1.20*	1	1.04	0.97	1.08	0.96	0.90	0.95	0.98
Fort Portal	0.92	0.98	–	0.95	0.86*	0.97*	1.01**	0.97	0.97	0.94	0.93	0.94
Kawaala	0.98	0.94	0.96	–	0.93	0.98	0.98	1.13	0.99*	0.80*	0.91	0.92
Kibuli	1.04	1.01*	1.15	1.05*	–	0.94	0.98	0.96	0.998*	1.00*	1.03	1.04
Kisenyi	0.96	0.96	0.98**	0.94	1	–	1.25*	0.99	0.96	1.06	1.03	0.99
Kiswa	0.96	1.56	0.97*	0.98	0.97*	0.93**	–	0.98	0.95	0.98	1.03	0.98
Kitebi	0.92	1.17	0.99	1.27	0.88	0.96	1.01	–	0.93	0.85	0.98	0.97
Koboko	0.98	0.97	0.998	1.07*	1.00	0.94	0.99	0.95	–	0.94	0.99	1.02
Mbarara	1.08	1.09	1.03	1.02	1.06	0.93	1.01	1.06	1.01	–	0.99	1.19**
Nsambya	0.98	1.02	0.98	1.02	0.997	0.98***	0.998	0.99	0.96	0.98	–	1.04
Tororo	0.94	0.99	0.96	0.98	0.91	0.96	0.95	0.91	0.92	0.98	0.76	–

Statistical support: *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the PA gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 33) but not in the PA gene.

Supplementary Table 64: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between location sites sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the PA gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (H3)												
	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	–	1.04	1.08	1.04	1.03	0.98*	0.98	0.99	0.999	1.04	1.04**	1.05
Entebbe	0.96	–	0.97	1.04*	0.96	0.97	0.95	0.98	0.93	0.90	0.97	0.93
Fort Portal	0.92	0.98	–	0.97	0.94*	0.98*	0.94**	0.95	0.94	0.95	0.94	0.94
Kawaala	0.93	0.92	0.97	–	0.85	1.02	0.98	1.10	0.94	0.84*	0.98	0.91
Kibuli	0.98	1.08	1.12*	1.12	–	0.99*	1.01	1.02	0.96*	1.04*	1.00	1.10
Kisenyi	0.96	1.13	1.01**	1.02	1.04	–	1.08*	0.999	0.95	0.98	0.97	0.98
Kiswa	0.99	1.26	1.04*	0.96	1.00*	0.96*	–	0.98	0.95	0.96	0.98	0.92
Kitebi	0.94	1.14	0.97	1.26	0.95	0.94	0.98	–	0.93	0.94	0.92	0.93
Koboko	0.99	1.00	1.06*	1.11*	1.04	1.02	0.98	1.02	–	1.04	0.98	1.07
Mbarara	1.05	1.21	1.12	1.18*	1.11	0.995	0.97	1.18	0.98	–	0.96	1.15*
Nsambya	1.01*	1.00	1.06	1.01	1.01	0.99**	0.95	1.02	0.95	0.99	–	1.01
Tororo	0.93	0.95	0.93	0.98	0.96	1.01	0.97	0.93	0.97	0.93	0.79	–

Statistical support: *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the H3 gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 33) but not in the H3 gene.

Supplementary Table 65: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between location sites sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the H3 gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (NP)												
ORIGIN	DESTINATION											
	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	–	1.05	1.14	1.04	1.05	0.99*	1.01	1.03	1.04	0.99	1.1**	1.07
Entebbe	0.95	–	0.95	0.98*	0.97	0.96	0.99	0.96	0.94	0.90	0.997	0.87
Fort Portal	0.90	1.01	–	0.97	0.91	0.98*	0.98**	0.99	0.93	0.99	0.98	0.94
Kawaala	0.95	0.98	0.95	–	0.94	0.98	0.999	1.14	0.90*	0.92*	0.98	0.997
Kibuli	1.01	1.01	1.17*	1.08	–	0.96*	1.00	1.03	0.97	1.01	1.04	1.12
Kisenyi	0.99	1.12	1.01*	1.00	0.98	–	1.21*	0.97	0.94	0.98	0.97	0.97
Kiswa	0.96	1.13	1.03*	0.97	0.99*	0.93**	–	0.96	0.88	0.99*	1.00	1.01
Kitebi	0.96	1.11	0.96	1.29	0.96	0.997	0.98	–	0.96	0.94	0.97	0.97
Koboko	1.01	1.07	1.05	0.99*	1.01	0.97	1.01	0.97	–	0.98*	0.99	0.99
Mbarara	1.03	1.13	1.08*	1.19	1.05	1.02	0.95	1.11	1.03	–	1.02	1.13*
Nsambya	0.97*	0.96	1.00	1.04	1.02	1.00**	1.02	1.04	0.97	0.91	–	1.02
Tororo	0.92	0.99	0.96	1.05	0.96	1.01	0.95	0.98	0.97	0.95	0.84	–

Statistical support: *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the NP gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 33) but not in the NP gene.

Supplementary Table 66: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between location sites sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the NP gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (N2)												
ORIGIN	DESTINATION											
	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	–	1.00	1.14	1.05	1.08	0.97	0.97	1.04	1.04	1.03	1.06**	1.05
Entebbe	0.97	–	0.97	1.01*	0.97	0.93	0.96	0.995	0.98*	0.93	1.02	0.87
Fort Portal	0.90	0.94	–	0.94	0.85	0.96*	0.94**	0.95	0.99	0.94	0.96	0.995
Kawaala	0.95	1.01*	0.95	–	0.91	1.01	0.97	1.13	0.98*	0.85	0.97	0.96
Kibuli	1.04	1.05	1.21*	1.05	–	0.98	1.00	1.03	0.98	1.04*	1.01	1.09
Kisenyi	1.00	1.09	0.96**	0.99	0.99	–	1.21*	0.97	0.91	0.97	0.999	0.96
Kiswa	0.94	1.44	0.96*	1.03	0.98*	0.92**	–	0.99	0.90	0.96*	0.99	0.94
Kitebi	0.93*	1.10	0.98	1.21	0.98	0.98	1.05	–	0.97	0.94	0.94	0.95
Koboko	1.03	0.99	0.96	0.98*	0.94	0.94	0.95	0.96	–	1.00	0.95	0.99
Mbarara	1.03	1.11	1.07	1.16	1.10*	0.99	1.02	1.07	1.04	–	1.07	1.10*
Nsambya	0.998	1.04	1.03	1.05	1.01	0.98**	1.01	0.98	0.99	1.02	–	1.00
Tororo	0.94	1.02	0.98	1.05	0.95	1.03	0.93	1.01	0.96	0.95	0.83	–

Statistical support: *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the N2 gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 33) but not in the N2 gene.

Supplementary Table 67: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between location sites sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the N2 gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (MP)												
	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	–	1.06	1.25	1.04	1.05	0.97*	1.01	1.00	1.03	1.01	1.05**	1.11
Entebbe	0.83	–	0.89	0.94*	0.96	0.97	1.02	0.96	0.83	0.88	0.98	0.91
Fort Portal	0.91	1.00	–	0.93	0.93*	0.99*	0.98** *	0.97	0.99	0.97	0.93	0.89
Kawaala	0.98	0.95	0.98	–	0.92	0.98	1.06	1.38	0.996*	0.85**	0.95	0.93
Kibuli	1.03	1.05	1.06*	1.29	–	1.02	0.98	1.09	1.02*	1.08	1.06	1.15
Kisenyi	0.99	0.93	1.00*	1.00	0.98	–	1.12	0.98*	0.94	1.01	0.99	0.98
Kiswa	0.998	0.95	0.98**	1.00	0.95*	0.94**	–	0.92	0.88*	0.97	0.93	0.97
Kitebi	0.95	1.30*	0.97	1.52*	0.92	0.99	1.00	–	0.94	0.90	0.96	0.99
Koboko	1.00	1.05	1.09*	1.04	1.00*	0.97	1.00	1.05	–	1.02*	0.97	1.08
Mbarara	0.999	1.10	1.01	1.30	1.06	0.98	0.93	1.04	0.98	–	0.99	1.02**
Nsambya	0.92*	1.02	0.96	1.02	1.01	0.97*	0.97*	0.97	0.96	0.97	–	1.08
Tororo	0.96	0.96	0.995	0.97	0.93	0.96	0.97	0.93	0.99	0.96	0.74	–

Statistical support: *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the MP gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 33) but not in the MP gene.

Supplementary Table 68: Migration rates of Uganda among A(H3N2) viruses between location sites sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the MP gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (NS)												
	DESTINATION											
ORIGIN	Arua	Entebbe	Fort Portal	Kawaala	Kibuli	Kisenyi	Kiswa	Kitebi	Koboko	Mbarara	Nsambya	Tororo
Arua	–	1.01	1.17	1.02	1.05	0.96*	0.99	1.04	1.05	1.03	1.05**	1.10
Entebbe	0.93	–	0.96	0.99*	0.97	0.99	0.98	0.93	0.92	0.94	0.95	0.89
Fort Portal	0.91	0.99	–	1.01	0.92*	0.98*	0.97*	1.02	0.94	0.93	0.95	1.00
Kawaala	0.96	1.02	0.90	–	0.92	1.01	0.98	1.10	0.98*	0.85*	0.97	0.93
Kibuli	0.98	1.06*	1.11*	1.12	–	1.01*	0.92	1.07	0.97	1.02*	1.08	1.1
Kisenyi	0.96	1.25	0.96*	0.998	0.96	–	1.15**	1.01	0.92	0.97	0.99	0.96
Kiswa	0.98	1.14	0.97**	1.00	0.98*	0.93*	–	1.00	0.86	1.03	0.97	0.97
Kitebi	0.89	1.10	0.96	1.30	0.99	0.97	0.97	–	0.92	0.88	0.94	0.91
Koboko	0.96	1.04	1.04*	1.02*	0.99	0.99	0.98	1.02	–	1.02*	1.02	0.99
Mbarara	1.04	1.20	1.07*	1.20	1.02	1.04	0.97	1.11	1.05	–	0.98	1.12*
Nsambya	0.95*	1.01	0.995	1.00	0.99	0.99*	0.99	1.00	1.01	0.96	–	1.01
Tororo	0.92	0.99	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84	–

Statistical support: *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the NS gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 33) but not in the NS gene.

Supplementary Table 69: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between location sites sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the NS gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (PB2)					
	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	0.92	1.23**	0.89	0.95
Central–Entebbe	0.90	-	1.43**	0.80	0.87
Central–Kampala	0.90***	0.82	-	0.80	0.70
Northwest	1.19	0.96*	1.13	-	1.23
Western	1.08	0.94	1.08	0.92*	-

Statistical support: * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes). **Rates highlighted** yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the PB2 gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 34A) but not in the PB2 gene.

Supplementary Table 70: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the PB2 gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (PB1)					
	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	1.01	1.28*	0.93	1.01
Central–Entebbe	0.92	-	1.22*	0.76	0.89
Central–Kampala	0.85**	0.68	-	0.87	0.73
Northwest	1.14	1.02*	1.13	-	1.20
Western	1.16	1.04	1.15	0.85*	-

Statistical support: * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes). **Rates highlighted** yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the PB1 gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 34A) but not in the PB1 gene.

Supplementary Table 71: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the PB1 gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (PA)					
	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	0.96	1.10**	0.94	1.01
Central–Entebbe	0.89	-	1.72*	0.77	0.90
Central–Kampala	0.87***	0.93	-	0.86	0.74
Northwest	1.13	0.96*	1.10	-	1.21
Western	1.11	0.91	1.01	0.89*	-

Statistical support: * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes). **Rates highlighted** yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the PA gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 34A) but not in the PA gene.

Supplementary Table 72: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the PA gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (H3)					
	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	0.97	1.20**	0.93*	0.99
Central–Entebbe	0.88	-	1.37*	0.82	0.89
Central–Kampala	0.89**	0.80	-	0.86	0.78
Northwest	1.13	1.06*	1.16*	-	1.12
Western	1.14	1.02	1.21	0.91	-

Statistical support: * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes). **Rates highlighted** yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the H3 gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 34A) but not in the H3 gene.

Supplementary Table 73: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the H3 gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (NP)					
	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	0.99*	1.41*	0.91	1.14*
Central–Entebbe	0.83	-	1.02*	0.75*	0.86
Central–Kampala	0.91***	0.65	-	0.88	0.86
Northwest	1.11	0.96*	1.07*	-	1.24
Western	1.14	0.93	1.28	0.88*	-

Statistical support: * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes). **Rates highlighted** yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the NP gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 34A) but not in the NP gene.

Supplementary Table 1: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 2010 and 2018, estimated from the NP gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (N2)					
	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	0.97*	1.35*	0.90	1.11
Central–Entebbe	0.88	-	1.35*	0.77*	0.87
Central–Kampala	0.88***	0.83	-	0.85	0.82
Northwest	1.06	0.98*	1.04*	-	1.17
Western	1.05	0.90	1.18	0.86*	-

Statistical support: * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the N2 gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 34A) but not in the N2 gene.

Supplementary Table 75: Migration rates of Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the N2 gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (MP)					
	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	0.95	1.41	0.92*	0.97*
Central–Entebbe	0.93	-	1.01**	0.67	0.87
Central–Kampala	0.95***	0.75	-	0.91	0.81
Northwest	1.13	0.96**	1.13	-	1.44
Western	1.32	0.95	0.99	0.93*	-

Statistical support: * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the MP gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 34A) but not in the MP gene.

Supplementary Table 76: Migration rates of Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the MP gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

MIGRATION RATE (NS)					
	DESTINATION				
ORIGIN	Eastern	Central–Entebbe	Central–Kampala	Northwest	Western
Eastern	-	0.96	1.33*	0.90*	1.02*
Central–Entebbe	0.84	-	1.09*	0.70	0.83
Central–Kampala	0.91***	0.80	-	0.88	0.84
Northwest	1.13	1.02*	1.12*	-	1.25
Western	1.13	0.96	1.23	0.86*	-

Statistical support: * $3 \leq BF < 10$ (supported routes), ** $10 \leq BF < 100$ (strongly supported routes), *** $100 \leq BF < 1000$ (very strongly supported routes), **** $BF \geq 1000$ (decisive routes). Rates highlighted yellows and reds show differences between the gene and WG. Specifically, yellows are the significant rates unique to the NS gene while the Reds show rates that were significant in the WG (supplementary Table 34A) but not in the NS gene.

Supplementary Table 77: Migration rates among Uganda A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 2010 and 2017, estimated from the NS gene sequences using the BSSVS model in BEAST1.

4.6 Migration rates among Africa A(H3N2) viruses

A. MUGRATION						
	DESTINATION					
ORIGIN	Central	Eastern	Northern	Southern	Uganda	Western
Central	–	0.1259	0.2649	0.1281	0.1341	0.1544
Eastern	0.2865	–	0.2982	0.4168	0.4312	0.4402
Northern	0.1072	0.053	–	0.1127	0.0446	0.0561
Southern	0.1799	0.2571	0.3908	–	0.067	0.2534
Uganda	0.3677	0.5195	0.3021	0.131	–	0.1249
Western	0.1809	0.2265	0.1623	0.2115	0.0534	–
B. BSSVS						
Central	–	0.989 (2.36E ⁻⁴ –2.885)	0.887 (8.29E ⁻⁴ –2.645)	0.982 (2.57E ⁻⁴ –2.843)	1.314** (1.15E ⁻³ –3.219)	0.994 (1.16E ⁻³ –2.963)
Eastern	0.765* (7.22E ⁻⁶ –2.379)	–	0.942 (5.18E ⁻⁴ –3.089)	0.902* (1.92E ⁻³ –2.329)	1.612**** (0.37–3.1197)	0.853* (1.07E ⁻³ –2.404)
Northern	1.01 (2.06E ⁻³ –2.959)	1.013 (1.65E ⁻⁴ –2.976)	–	1.034 (7.61E ⁻⁴ –3.176)	1.011 (1.87E ⁻⁴ –2.971)	1.066 (4.36E ⁻⁴ –3.284)
Southern	1.051* (1.26E ⁻³ –2.754)	2.125** (1.52E ⁻³ –4.688)	0.719* (4.97E ⁻⁴ –2.258)	–	0.917 (2.01E ⁻⁴ –2.734)	1.352** (1.17E ⁻³ –3.196)
Uganda	0.747 (1.91E ⁻⁴ –2.519)	0.8*** (0.1353–1.6119)	0.932 (1.24E ⁻³ –2.842)	0.902 (2.12E ⁻³ –2.729)	–	0.898 (1.5E ⁻⁴ –2.939)
Western	0.503** (0.0108–1.275)	1.072** (9.79E ⁻⁴ –2.446)	0.868 (3.45E ⁻⁴ –2.650)	0.704** (6.4E ⁻⁴ –1.614)	0.968 (6.53E ⁻⁴ –2.972)	–
C. MASCOT						
Central	–	0.145 (7.8E ⁻⁶ –0.465)	0.0674 (3.53E ⁻⁶ –0.212)	0.1433 (1.16E ⁻⁴ –0.441)	0.9478 (0.0913–2.0635)	0.0434 (1.87E ⁻⁵ –0.1336)
Eastern	0.1484 (4.53E ⁻⁵ –0.436)	–	0.0593 (4.94E–6, 0.1912)	0.1196 (1.54E ⁻⁵ –0.386)	0.1961 (1.47E ⁻⁵ –0.532)	0.0425 (2.96E ⁻⁵ –0.131)
Northern	0.2635 (4.63E ⁻⁵ –0.675)	0.38 (4.80E ⁻⁵ –1.0624)	–	0.9708 (1.83E ⁻³ –1.87)	0.2224 (4.67E ⁻⁵ –0.563)	1.1983 (4.25E ⁻⁴ –3.091)
Southern	0.2545 (5.17E ⁻⁴ –0.677)	0.5174 (1.52E ⁻⁵ –1.417)	0.1417 (6.1591E–6, 0.494)	–	0.1653 (4.26E ⁻⁵ –0.489)	0.0919 (1.15E ⁻⁵ –0.294)
Uganda	0.1915 (8.04E ⁻⁵ –0.637)	0.1068 (4.64E ⁻⁵ –0.317)	0.0588 (3.3E ⁻⁶ –0.183)	0.0991 (1.69E ⁻⁵ –0.308)	–	0.0461 (3.47E ⁻⁶ –0.141)
Western	0.2517 (3.28E ⁻⁴ –0.638)	0.1484 (7.59E ⁻⁵ –0.482)	0.2573 (1.04E ⁻⁴ –0.921)	0.2614 (8.52E ⁻⁶ –0.873)	0.1385 (3.91E ⁻⁶ –0.406)	–

Supplementary Table 2: Migration rates among Africa A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 1994 and 2021, estimated from the whole genome sequences using the TreeTime Migration, BSSVS and MASCOT models. For the BSSVS analysis, highlighted blue and bold are rates with high statistical support. *3 ≤BF <10 (supported routes), ** 10≤BF<100 (strongly supported routes), ***100≤BF<1000 (very strongly supported routes), **** BF≥1000 (decisive routes).

4.7 Migration rates among global A(H3N2) viruses

ORIGIN	DESTINATION					
	Africa	Asia	Europe	North America	Oceania	South America
Africa	–	0.0637 (2.3E ⁻⁵ –0.209)	0.1981 (0.024–0.464)	0.1142 (1.78E ⁻⁵ –0.245)	0.0521 (6.47E ⁻⁶ –0.095)	0.0621 (3.78E ⁻⁶ –0.172)
Asia	0.069 (2.7E ⁻⁵ –0.2)	–	0.9715 (1.64E ⁻⁴ –2.558)	0.23 (1.85E ⁻⁴ –0.726)	0.6254 (5.52E ⁻⁶ –1.373)	0.262 (5.25E ⁻⁵ –0.739)
Europe	0.1542 (1.59E ⁻⁴ –0.407)	0.124 (7.58E ⁻⁶ –0.531)	–	0.5487 (5.05E ⁻⁵ –1.616)	1.0995 (4.15E ⁻⁵ –3.251)	0.212 (4.22E ⁻⁵ –0.603)
North America	0.0285 (1.79E ⁻⁵ –0.089)	0.0449 (4.82E ⁻⁵ –0.17)	0.3035 (6.94E ⁻⁵ –0.904)	–	0.0293 (1.73E ⁻⁵ –0.085)	0.5584 (1.97E ⁻⁴ –1.0778)
Oceania	0.2474 (1.55E ⁻⁴ –0.478)	3.2662 (1.385 –7.299)	1.5527 (5.82E ⁻⁴ –3.558)	1.3739 (0.044–2.064)	–	0.4823 (4.05E ⁻³ –0.958)
South America	0.0265 (5.95E ⁻⁵ –0.072)	0.0575 (1.12E ⁻⁵ –0.146)	0.0872 (5.72E ⁻⁵ –0.2983)	0.0895 (2.52E ⁻⁵ –0.273)	0.0441 (1.68E ⁻⁶ –0.061)	–

Supplementary Table 79: Migration rates among global A(H3N2) viruses between geographical regions sampled between 1968 and 2021, estimated from the WG sequences using the MASCOT models.